

Thesis for the Degree of Master of Science in Construction Management
**Practicability Assessment of Smart Village in the Hilly
Region of Nepal**

Rajat Pokhrel
(2019-1-06-0024)

School of Engineering
Faculty of Science and Technology
Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal
Joint Constituent College of Pokhara University
Urlabari -3, Morang

September, 2021

Thesis for the Degree of Master of Science in Construction Management
**Practicability Assessment of Smart Village in the Hilly
Region of Nepal**

Supervised by Assoc. Prof. Anjay Kumar Mishra, Ph.D.

A thesis submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the degree of
Master of Science in Construction Management

**Rajat Pokhrel
(2019-1-06-0024)**

**School of Engineering
Faculty of Science and Technology
Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal
Joint Constituent College of Pokhara University
Urlabari -3, Morang**

September, 2021

DECLARATION

I hereby declare that this study entitled **Practicability Assessment of Smart Village in the Hilly Region of Nepal** is based on my original research work. Related works on the topic, by other researchers, have been duly acknowledged. I owe all the liabilities relating to the accuracy and authenticity of the data or any other information included hereunder.

Signature:

Name of the Student: Rajat Pokhrel

P.U. Registration Number: 2019-1-06-0024

Date:

RECOMMENDATION

This is to certify that this thesis entitled **Practicability Assessment of Smart Village in the Hilly Region of Nepal** prepared and submitted by Mr. Rajat Pokhrel, in partial fulfillment of the requirements of the degree of **Master of Science (M.Sc.) in Construction Management** awarded by Pokhara University, and has been completed under my supervision. I recommend the same for acceptance by Pokhara University.

Signature:

Name of the supervisor: Assoc. Prof. Anjay Kumar Mishra, Ph.D.

Organization: Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy Nepal

Designation: Research Director

Date:

CERTIFICATE

This thesis entitled “**Practicability Assessment of Smart Village in the Hilly Region of Nepal**” prepared and submitted by **Rajat Pokhrel** has been examined by us and is accepted for the award of the degree of Master of Science (M.Sc.) in Construction Management by Pokhara University.

.....
External Examiner

.....
Signature

.....
Date

Assoc. Prof. Anjay Kumar Mishra, Ph.D.
Supervisor

.....
Signature

.....
Date

Assoc. Prof. Anjay Kumar Mishra, Ph.D.
Research Director
Madan Bhandari Memorial Academy
Nepal

.....
Signature

.....
Date

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

I would like to express my sincere gratitude to my supervisor Assoc. Prof. Anjay Kumar Mishra, Ph.D., Research Director of MBMAN for his invaluable guidance, patience, kindness, and constant support without which I may not have reached this point. I am deeply impressed with his wealth of knowledge and his motivating attitude.

I also acknowledge the help and support of Mr. Chudamani Timsina, Director of MBMAN, all the faculty members of MBMAN, and all the people who helped me while completing my post-graduate studies. I am also thankful to Er. Manoj Kumar Singh, Mr. Yubaraj Bhatta, Architect Umesh Dhimal, Er. Ram Bhatta for their comments during different phases of internal defence as a faculty member of MBMAN.

I would also like to express my sincerest gratitude to my parents, family members, and friends for their direct/indirect support and encouragement throughout this thesis work especially.

Similarly, I am very much grateful to all my respondents for kind cooperation without whom this study would not have been completed.

There are other helping hands in this research study. I would like to express my gratitude to all concerned people for their cooperation.

Signature:

Name of Student: Rajat Pokhrel

P.U. Registration Number: 2019-1-06-0024

Date:

ABSTRACT

Villages are the backbone of the nation and a smart village means such a village that can provide various services needed in day-to-day life to the villagers effectively and efficiently. The overall objective of this research is to assess the practicability of the smart village in the hilly region of Nepal with a special reference to **Sandakpur Rural Municipality**. The study covered the locality within **Maipokhari and Sulubung village of Sandakpur Rural Municipality**. A scheduled questionnaire survey was done with 45 respondents under the pandemic of COVID-19 to find the present status of the health, education, governance, services, water supply, irrigation in the area along with their perception of smart village practicability. From the literature review of the various paper about smart villages throughout the world, some of the characteristics were adopted and these were assessed in the study area. Five points Likert scale was used on ranking smart village feature and Chi-Square test is done to determine the significance of respondent's opinions for the variables from the collected data followed by benefit-cost ratio, NPV and IRR for economic feasibility.

After the analysis of data with the Five-Point Likert Scale, ratings on smart features like Smart Utilization of Resources, Smart Living, Smart Governance, Smart Village Services, Smart Technology, Smart Tourism, and Gender Equity and Women Equity were given as Fair (2.82), Fair (3.02), Fair (2.93), Fair (3.17), Fair (3.2), Good (2.42) and Poor (3.46) respectively. The chi-square test showed that the majority of respondents supported the perspective toward Smart Village features as fair. B/C ratio was found as 4.98 and 2.85 at 6.5% and 10% discount rate, NPV was found as Rs 1,550,474,977 and Rs 715,758,502.7 at 6.5% and 10% discount rate and IRR was found as 18.32 % for 30 year analysis period which assures smart village can be a better option for the sustainable village.

Smart villages can only be possible with long-term planning, strategy and investment. With the adoption of features of the smart village, the study area can be converted into a smart village but it may take time to incorporate these features completely. Only with a gradual development of infrastructures and facilities, Maipokhari and Sulubung villages of Sandakpur Rural Municipality and even other villages can be developed as smart village. But the different village has a different characteristic, so the development model of one village could be only a reference for the further analysis of a particular village.

Keywords: Smart Village, Information Technology, Sustainable Development, Equity, Services

Contents

DECLARATION.....	i
RECOMMENDATION	ii
CERTIFICATE	iii
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	iv
ABSTRACT.....	v
Chapter-1.....	1
INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 Background	1
1.2 Statement of the Problem	2
1.3 Research Questions	3
1.4 Research Objectives	3
1.5 Significance of the Study	3
1.6 Scope and Limitation of the Study.....	4
Chapter-2.....	5
LITERATURE REVIEW	5
2.1 Theoretical Review	5
2.2 Empirical Review.....	10
2.3 Research Gap	15
Chapter-3.....	16
METHODOLOGY	16
3.1 Study Area	16
3.2 Research Approach	18
3.3 Sampling and Population	18
3.4 Data Collection	19
3.5 Analysis of Data.....	20
3.6 Framework and Flowchart for the Study	24
3.7 Summary of Research Methodology	25
Chapter-4.....	26
RESULT AND DISCUSSION	26

4.1 Idea of Smart Village	26
4.2 Technological Development Plan	30
4.3 Economic Feasibility of Smart Village.....	42
4.4 Discussion Using SWOT Analysis on Practicability of Smart Village	51
Chapter 5	56
CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION.....	56
5.1 Key Findings.....	56
5.2 Conclusion	56
5.3 Recommendation	57
5.4 Recommendation for Further Study.....	57
REFERENCES	58

List of Figures

Figure 3.1: GIS Map of Study Area.....	17
Figure 3.2: Study Area.....	18
Figure 3.3: Framework and Flowchart for the Study.....	24
Figure 4.1: Location of Municipality with Land Cover.....	33
Figure 4.2: Main Source of Income generation	35
Figure 4.3: Housing Condition	36
Figure 4.4: Fuel for Cooking	36
Figure 4.5: Education and IT	37
Figure 4.6: Health Service	37
Figure 4.7: GIS Map of Proposed Components Location.....	38
Figure 4.8: Likert Scale Chart Showing Percentage of Respondents	40

List of Tables

Table 2.1: Smart Village Concept.....	5
Table 2.2: Traditional Design versus Smart Design	7
Table 2.3: Literature Review	12
Table 3.1: Summary of Research Methodology	25
Table 4.1: Population Distribution.....	31
Table 4.2: Questionnaire and Responses	34
Table 4.3: Likert Scale Table.....	39
Table 4.4: Result of Chi-Square Test.....	41

Table 4.5: Assumed Cost	43
Table 4.6: B/C Ratio, NPV and IRR Analysis.....	47
Table 4.7: SWOT Analysis	51

List of Appendices

Appendix A: Respondent Opinion on Smart Village Features.....	63
Appendix B: Questionnaires	66
Appendix C: Observed Frequency and Expected Frequency for Chi-Square Test	82
Appendix D: Some Pictures and Photograph.....	83

Abbreviations

CBS: Central Bureau of Statistics
 CCTV: Closed Circuit Television
 CGI: Corrugated Galvanised Iron
 ENRD: European Network for Rural Development
 FDG: Focus Group Discussions
 GIS: Geographic Information System
 GPS: Global Positioning System
 GESI: Gender Equality and Social Inclusion
 ICT: Information Communication and Technology
 IEEE: Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers
 INGO: International Non-governmental Organization
 IRR: Internal Rate of Return
 IT: Information Technology
 KII: Key Informant Interview
 MOFAGA: Ministry of Federal Affairs & General Administration
 MARR: Minimum Attractive Rate of Return
 NGO: Non-governmental Organization
 NPV: Net Present Value
 PMAMP: Prime Minister Agriculture Modernization Project
 RCC: Reinforced Cement Concrete
 SDG: Sustainable Development Goals
 SPSS: Statistical Package for Social Science
 SRM: Sandakpur Rural Municipality
 SRN: Strategic Road Network
 TEL: Technology Enhanced Learning
 UN: United Nations
 VDC: Village Development Committee

Chapter-1

INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Nepal is a country with diverse geographic environments, including *Terai* (plain area), Hill, and Mountain, but in all these areas, the urbanization style is fast and uneven. The urbanization style is restricted normally in Kathmandu Valley and other some restrained cities of *Terai*. The result is that most of the massive cities are failing to cope with the demand of infrastructure offerings and job possibilities also are more and more dazzling beneath the penalties of the haphazard urbanization. In these large cities environmental degradation, congestion, city poverty, scattered settlements, unemployment and lagging provisions of infrastructure offerings have emerged as an increasingly more seen phenomenon (Mishra. A.K and Shah, 2018).

Except for the Kathmandu Valley and its surrounding areas, most cities and regions in Nepal still have no economic growth and no intention of investment. Urban centers are already facing pent-up demand for infrastructure services. Due to the limited fiscal foundation and other weak municipal capacities, the demand for catching up is also increasing. Therefore, urban investment is still largely uncoordinated and scattered, and is used to provide basic facilities, rather than strategic projects that have a greater impact on the regional economy. The greater part of the settlement is in the hilly region of Nepal as it covers about 68% of the absolute territory. In any case, the greater part of the settlements are distant and in reverse because of the absence of least improvement amenities. The reality of the matter is that it is exceptionally hard to overhaul country towns to created urban communities as there are dispersed settlements and the majority of the amenities effectively available in urban can be costly because of geological conditions (Poudel, 2013).

Smart villages are one of the ideas of developed villages in India. This idea was proposed by Viswanadham and Vedula in their book "Smart Village Design". Smart villages imitate the smart city model, integrating innovation and renewal in remote areas (Abinash and Josephine, 2018). The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), embraced in 2015, submitted the worldwide advancement network to 17 inter-related objectives and 169 indicators concentrated on improving personal satisfaction for all. The SDGs' vision, objectives, and targets are likewise centered on reviving rustic social orders and their numerous connections with urban focuses (UN, 2015).

A smart village is an all-encompassing and comprehensive methodology for country advanced change towards accomplishing the SDGs in far-off and underserved communities where: a) Rural inhabitants approach organize foundation using associated gadgets and services. b) Citizens can get to significant and groundbreaking SDG-related advanced administrations, as they need them, on schedule, anyplace, and constantly. c) Services are modified for the particular SDG needs of residents. d) Integrated SDG-related administrations are persistently improving and adjusting to changes. e) Partner associations included are consistently learning and adjusting their administrations (ITU, 2020).

Rapid urbanization is a continuous unique procedure and is the most prevailing wonder in every single developing nation and Nepal is no special case. The proclaimed Constitution of Nepal has rebuilt the state with an aggregate of 753 local level structures comprising of 6 metropolitan cities, 11 Sub-Metropolitan cities, 276 municipalities and 460 rural municipalities over the seven provinces (MOFAGA, 2018). With the ongoing expansion of regions, metropolitan territories are evaluated to house around two-third of Nepal's population. Additionally, the rebuilding and political decision is ready to follow the way to success and urbanization. Urbanization brings about fast population development followed by pressure on the interest for occupations, lodging, clean water, transportation, social administrations among others. The legislature just as metropolitan specialists faces difficulties to guarantee the financial and social prosperity of individuals dwelling in the region. This has made a mounting need to oversee and improve metropolitan frameworks and administrations.

The planned urban development in Nepal since its introduction in 1952, has embraced a few arranging devices including Physical Development Plan, Integrated Action Planning, Periodic Plans, and so forth (Poudel, 2013). The significant difficulties looked by urban territories are overseeing fast urbanization, foundation improvement while trying to make it maintainable and reasonable. Rather than endeavouring just for physical arranging, it is imperative to discover new and more astute approaches to adapt to expanding urban issues and upgrade resident's life through Information and Communication Technology (ICT). The point of the smart village was to assist it with taking care of all issues through the usage of ICT and Geographic Information System (GIS) (Ahlawat, 2017).

1.2 Statement of the Problem

The idea of Smart Cities concentrates especially on large information and the open doors for changing how urban areas work through related advanced innovations. Smart villages are not just an expansion of this; they center rather after enabling nearby communities to draw in with their future, including the utilization of computerized advancements (ENRD, 2019).

In Nepal, the municipalities are generally small and are given city status by consolidating a few Village Development Committee (VDCs). Indeed, the vast majority of the regions show rural characters, and the issues confronted are essentially contrasted with enormous urban communities of the populace at least 100,000. Most of the village lacks basic infrastructures like clean drinking water, sanitation, irrigation facilities and electricity. “**Sandakpur Rural Municipality**” located in the eastern part of Nepal Shares a border with India and also has very famous tourist spots but lacks basic infrastructures and services while it is considered deeply. Although agriculture is the basic occupation of this rural municipality and having potential for the medicinal herb industry people are backward as they even don't have their land and lack basic needs like clean drinking water, irrigation, and even ICT-based services.

The smart village enables its residents to take advantage of contemporary innovations and social achievements, while its framework is still established within the framework of the Sustainable Development Goals, providing an opportunity to effectively respond to possible security destiny

and neighbourhood issues, as well as economic. To regard villages as a self-ruling and free and guarantee legitimate sanitation facility, good education, better foundation, clean drinking water, health facilities, environmental protection, resource use efficiency, sustainable power source, there is a need to characterize and adjust the operational meaning of Smart Village, explicitly to the Nepalese context.

1.3 Research Questions

The main Research Question is:

- What is that the practicableness of the smart village in the hilly region of Nepal?

The research question is divided into several sub-questions. These constitute:

- How to build up a thought of the smart village concept with an institutional development plan in the Nepalese Context with a case of Sandakpur Rural Municipality?
- What are the technological advancements needed for the progression of the smart village with the case of Sandakpur Rural Municipality?
- What is the economic feasibility of Sandakpur Rural Municipality for the advancement as a smart village?

1.4 Research Objectives

The main objective of the research is to assess the practicability of the smart village in the hilly region of Nepal with a case of Sandakpur Rural Municipality.

The specific objectives of this research are outlined, as below:

- To develop an idea of the smart village with an institutional development plan and its integral features/attributes in the Nepalese context each for countrywide and local level via a literature assessment of worldwide practice centered on developing countries.
- To analyze the technological advancement needed for the progression of the smart village with a case of Sandakpur Rural Municipality.
- To assess economic feasibility for the advancement as a smart village with a case of Sandakpur Rural Municipality.

1.5 Significance of the Study

This research can provide basic knowledge about the creation of smart villages with the goal that individuals dwelling there can have the option to get all the essential facilities like power, great streets, clean drinking water, sanitation, smart hospitals, media transmission, Technology Enhanced Learning (TEL), smart cultivating less expensively and efficiently so individuals living there can inspire their living style and don't consider movement. For the policymakers and institutions who work in this field, this research could be a guiding document to formulate and

regulate plans and policies. As of that conventional living, the condition can likewise be secured alongside current improved offices, and the issue of erratic urbanization can be explained.

1.6 Scope and Limitation of the Study

Following are the scope of the study:

- The study focuses on the development of the possibility of a smart village in the Nepalese setting at a local level.
- Extensive literature research has been done for incorporating a contextual requirement for the development of a smart village.
- Preparation of GIS-based maps showing all the topical regions such as physical development plan, land use plan, and infrastructure development plan.
- Economic analysis of study area for the advancement as a smart village.

As with most researches, this research brings along limitations as well. These are defined here:

- The study is restricted distinctly to some particular settlement territories or villages of Maipokhari, and Sulubung territory.
- The study is concentrated on the spot explicit boundaries for smartness as per the consultation with the provincial government, local government, stakeholder organizations, and inhabitants.
- The study doesn't cover all 17 inter-related objectives and 169 indicators of the United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDG) and also 4 pillars, 31 components, and 117 indicators for the study of Smart City according to the Ministry of Urban Development, Nepal Government however simply spread very few indicators that is under the task financial plan and accessible resources.

Chapter-2 LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Review

Smart Village is a concept developed for remote rural areas. It provides solutions to all problems that arise and improves the quality of life of the people living there. The Smart Village will provide the necessary framework for everyone's development to lead a quality life of respect, equality, happiness and education, safety and livelihood. It will also create a perfect and feasible state through the use of smart solutions. The smart village was created through five overlapping approaches: Redevelopment, Retrofitting, Greenfields, E-Pan, and livelihood (Eco Needs Foundation, 2016).

Table 2.1: Smart Village Concept

S	Social, Skilled and Simple	No discrimination on any tribe, caste and religion, everyone is literate and Skilled with Simple living and high thinking.
M	Moral, Methodical and Modern	Moral of Mahatma Gandhi, Swami Vivekananda and so forth Methodical utilizing total literacy and most recent methods Modern like urban areas.
A	Aware, Adaptive and Adjusting	The most significant level of awareness on worldwide social, economic and financial issues .Adaptive and adjusting to quickly changing conditions.
R	Responsive and Ready	Responsive to aggregate intelligence, development and bigger social issues Ready to produce own assets for independence and self-reliance.
T	Techno-Savvy and Transparent	Techno-Savvy for IT and Mobile usage Transparent in harmonic relations and delivery of services.

(Rutuja, 2016, A.Tripathi, 2019)

The United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs), embraced in 2015, committed the worldwide advancement of local areas to 17 inter-related goals and 169 targets focused on improving personal satisfaction for all. The SDGs and their objectives are likewise centered on rejuvenating rural communities and their connections with urban areas. The United Nations has expressed Sustainable Development Goals as:

“**GOAL 1: No Poverty:** End poverty in the entirety of its structures all over.
GOAL 2: Zero Hunger: End hunger, accomplish food security and improved sustenance and advance maintainable farming.
GOAL 3: Good Health and Well-being: Ensure healthy lives and advance prosperity for all.
GOAL 4: Quality Education: Ensure comprehensive and fair quality schooling and advance long-lasting learning openings for all.
GOAL 5: Gender Equality: Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls
GOAL 6: Clean Water and Sanitation
 Ensure accessibility and reasonable administration of water and sanitation for all.
GOAL 7: Affordable and Clean Energy: Ensure admittance to moderate, dependable, manageable, and present-day energy for all.
GOAL 8: Decent Work and Economic Growth: Promote supported, comprehensive and feasible economic development, full and productive employment and good work for all.
GOAL 9: Industry, Innovation, and Infrastructure: Build a strong foundation, advance comprehensive and manageable industrialization and cultivate development.
GOAL 10: Reduced Inequality: Reduce inequality inside and among nations.
GOAL 11: Sustainable Cities and Communities: Make urban communities and human settlements comprehensive, protected, strong and manageable.
GOAL 12: Responsible Consumption and Production
 Ensure supportable utilization and production patterns.
GOAL 13: Climate Action: Take critical activity to battle environmental change and its effects.
GOAL 14: Life below Water: Conserve and economically utilize the seas, oceans and marine assets for sustainable development.
GOAL 15: Life on Land: Protect, reestablish and advance practical utilization of earthly biological systems.
GOAL 16: Peace and Justice Strong Institutions: Promote tranquil and comprehensive social orders for sustainable development.
GOAL 17: Partnerships to Achieve the Goal: Strengthen the execution methods and renew the Global Partnership for Sustainable Development” (United Nations SDGs, 2015).

2.1.1 Smart Village

A smart village is a local area in country territories that use advanced network, arrangements, and assets for its development and change towards accomplishing the SDGs. They built on their existing local resources and opportunities to take part in a cycle of feasible improvement of their locality. They depend on a participatory way to develop and execute their strategies to improve their economic, social, and ecological conditions, specifically by advancing innovations also, mobilizing solutions offered by digital innovations. The commencement and the execution of smart village systems may expand on existing activities and can be financed by an assortment of public and private sources.

Connectivity of rural territory to urban alone can't convey ideal rural resident administration. Strong authority, political will, solid partnership, multi-partner engagement, resident-focused projects are among the basic requirements that will guarantee that the digital network infrastructure can convey sustainable development of comprehensive and fair administrations.

A smart village can focus on digital transformation in the following sectors:

- **Health:** The modernization of telemedicine and advanced digital health service will allow patients to have distant consultations and medical care workers to convey proficient services.
- **Security:** The installation of CCTV, digital applications and services for local law enforcement can share real-time information to keep locality safe.
- **Education:** The access to open and distance learning openings will empower capacity building for teachers and school administration just as giving impartial admittance to quality proficiency, long-lasting skills and learning for youngsters, youth and grown-ups.
- **Job Opportunity:** Services that can help jobless people to find a job and upgrade their employment skills.
- **Banking:** Access to digital banking and investment for residents and local businesses.
- **Agriculture:** Digital agriculture can uphold efficient and productive cultivating capacities among farmers (ITU 2020).

2.1.2 Traditional Design versus Smart Design

Traditional design methods have neglected to settle the absolute most squeezing issues on the world's rural and hilly regions. A Smart design approach is a socially determined approach that withdraws profoundly from traditional design and execution components of rural development projects.

Table 2.2: Traditional Design versus Smart Design

S.N.	Traditional Design	Smart Design
1	Top-down, various levelled designs, management, and dynamic.	Distributed, organized administration structures and dynamics.
2	Each area and service work separately utilizing divided technologies.	Incorporation of different sectors areas to focus on resident experience utilizing innovative technologies.
3	Unbending and rule-bound.	Adaptable and versatile to change.
4	Numerous layers of the executives and decision-making.	Smooth decision-making.
5	Partners working on their own to accomplish limited objectives.	Multi-partner integration, coordinated effort and aggregate activity towards shared objectives.
6	Taking care of issues individually.	An all-encompassing perspective including various elements of sustainability.
7	Duplication of ventures and infrastructure among various services and ventures.	Shared and re-utilized infrastructure and ventures.

(ITU,2020)

2.1.3 Worldwide Strategies on Smart Village

Several strategies are promoting the concept of smart villages worldwide. Smart Village Initiative: new thinking of global off-grid communities and IEEE Smart Villages: Empowering off-grid communities, in general, is full of vitality and strives to achieve Sustainable Development Goal 2030, especially Goal 7, Affordable and Clean Energy

The first is to increase access to sustainable energy, use it as the main driving force for improving good education and medical conditions, access to clean water, sanitation, economic development, improving safety, gender equality. The main vision of the initiative is to find a broader and more coordinated way to provide energy to rural areas, involving the government, education sector and the private sector. The implementation of the initiative is carried out in six major regions, more precisely in East Africa, West Africa, South Asia, Southeast Asia, South and Central America, the Caribbean, Mexico, so-called developing countries with limited educational prospects, electrical, economic and other Framework conditions. To find the most sensible arrangement, there are a large number of experts in the field to deal with, and even more: locals, non-governmental organizations, development organizations, business visionaries, political decision-makers, experts and experts in the humanities field. Their search for solutions also includes based on years of research, checking local and regional conditions, identifying cross-domain problems and proposing reasonable solutions.

Similarly, the IEEE Smart Village Project hopes to promote the development of off-grid communities through training and the creation of sustainable enterprises in the energy sector. The initiative was originally established as a Community Solutions Initiative (2009) and took over its current name in 2014. These exercises are spread all over the world and currently serve more than 50,000 people living in 34 villages in the African continent (such as Benin, Cameroon, Kenya, Malawi, Namibia, Nigeria, South Sudan, Zambia), in addition to Haiti and India.

2.1.4 Requirements for Smart Village Development

Building a smart village requires a change in the attitude of government leaders, directors and authorities, accomplices and partner associations to work collaboratively towards common objectives.

An entire of-government approach is required

An entire of-government approach is an all-encompassing and incorporated technique for arranging, planning, and conveying government services. It expects the government to organize across furthermore, among services and government authoritative constructions to cooperate on policy development, resident commitment, and delivery of service. This methodology is cost proficient, especially with framework, or venture, shared by all administration divisions, undertakings, and activities. It will permit the thought of a complete 360-degree perspective on resident requirements and the arrangement of a coordinated arrangement of administrations that react to various parts of prosperity and job. An entire of-government approach isn't just focused at a public pastoral level yet additionally at the municipality and village level where the distinctive municipality and village specialists work together on joint activities. It is based on the fact that:

- One office or service can presently don't tackle complex advancement challenges all alone.

- Invest in digital platforms and services can be applied across areas and offices, coming about in far more noteworthy utilizing of speculations, and along these lines making public scale-up conceivable from a resourcing viewpoint.
- Each organization or service can contribute special talents, abilities, and aptitude towards aggregate critical reasoning and problem-solving.
- Wasteful expenditure on unwanted resources and enlarged authoritative designs can be diminished.
- Operational, administration, business cycle, and cost efficiencies can be acquired for all government and public assistance delivery.
- An assembled, composed exertion to total interest in government can help fabricate arranging power, both for cost efficiencies and terms, while drawing in and haggling with non-state partners, for example, the private sector and donor agencies.
- A culture of sharing and communitarian critical thinking can be created inside the public authority.

Notwithstanding, adopting an entire of-government approach implies that government should challenge profoundly settled agencies and regional behaviour intentionally. Doing so implies that the government should:

- Comprehend the hierarchical societies and motivating forces that give rise to regional and local agency behaviour to create methodologies that support a sharing and communitarian culture.
- Build up a clear understanding of the particular manners by which coordination will work across various services and government organizations.
- Assemble trust, develop information on various offices and services inside government and develop facilitation and coordinated effort abilities within government (Ojo and Janowski, 2010).

The smart village concept proposes a cycle of growing a culture of communitarian critical thinking through entire of-government endeavours on the side of the SDGs through digital change (ITU, 2020).

2.2 Empirical Review

Several empirical types of research are found to be conducted in this area.

2.2.1 Smart village Features Based on Empirical Research

1) David Freshwater (2000), in his paper, suggested sustainable development is done while considering the environment, but from the perspective of rural communities, manageable improvements must be made to how individuals in the community earn income to maintain their rural lifestyle. In situations where companies are seen as a feature of supporting competency dialogue, long-term employment is repeatedly considered. In any case, the truth of contemporary rural and urban life is that the financial situation is changing rapidly, so it is necessary to have a dialogue about actual business in a unique environment. As the business world changes currency conditions, different types of work are also developing. On a basic level, advertising signs can provide data and conditions for this unique process. The basic principle of the paper is that the idea of the country and region makes it far-fetched for the economic sector to allow feasible work

2) Zhao Zhifeng (2009), in this paper pointed out the characteristics and problems of rural areas in the Beijing metropolitan area. This article examines the role of villages in metropolitan areas in the process of urbanization. According to the classification guidelines, the village system plan aims to deal with the future of village development under urbanization, to realize the sustainable development of rural areas.

3) N. Viswanadham, SowmyaVedula (2010), in this article describes the ecosystem of a village and then outlines the integrated design process for smart village construction. They define a smart village as a series of services that are effectively and efficiently provided to residents and businesses. Building a smart village requires a variety of services, including construction, agriculture, electricity, medical care, water, retail, manufacturing, and logistics. Intelligent information and technology play an important role in the design, delivery and monitoring of services. All the technologies and techniques needed to build smart villages are now available, some of which are already used in villages in India, but these are different, fragmented, segmented efforts. This paper recognizes that strategy, comprehensive planning, and most importantly, the use of appropriate governance models to monitor and execute activities are daily tasks. Their comprehensive design is a way to solve the population deficit and achieve the goal of inclusive growth. To build smart villages in other parts of the world this paper can be used as a reference.

4) Dr. Milind Kulkarni (2015), explained in this paper that in India, most of the population still lives in villages. In rural areas, the problem of solid waste is not as serious as in urban areas because of its lower power generation capacity. A lot of work needs to be done to clean up the village. He also discussed various aspects of cleaning the village, such as water supply, sanitation, indoor air quality, waste management and renewable energy. We can learn many lessons from the success and failure of introducing different alternatives. To keep in touch with technology, the clean village

project should combine technology and digital design to make the village not only clean but also smart. This article discusses all these aspects related to Maharashtra and India. This article plans to provide policymakers with important inputs and alternatives so that they can readjust and reformulate policies. The paper also recommends the effective creation of a clean and smart village.

5) Rutuja Somwanshi, Utkarsha Shindepatil, Deepali Tule, Archana Mankar, and Namdev Ingle (2016), presented in their project report the exploration and development of smart villages. They said that a smart village is a set of services that are effectively and efficiently provided to residents and businesses. "Smart Village" is modern energy access that catalyzes the development of education, health, safety, productive enterprises and the environment, which in turn supports the further improvement of energy access. In this report, they focus on improving the efficiency of resource utilization, local autonomy, access to basic convenience facilities, and responsible behaviour of individuals and communities, through the use of smart technologies and services to create smart villages with smart choices to build a happy society.

6) Bhagya Niranjambhai Patel, Prof. Rinni Shah (2017), in the case study of Kolavada Village in Gandhinagar Taluka, Gandhinagar District, Gujarat, India, concluded that, with the provision or upgrading of solid and sanitary facilities, such as disposal and sanitation facilities, promotes the development of the village, improves the standard of living and employment, and helps the village become rich and smart, and reduce migration from village to city. Smart villages produce goods and services for the local rural market and produce high-quality agricultural and rural industrial products for the domestic and international markets, which will become a supplementary engine for the economic growth of a village to city. They will also act as managers of the environment and, in some cases, as hubs for ecotourism. Try to provide or improve such solid waste treatment facilities, sanitation facilities and cleaning facilities between the development and upgrading of the village. Government plans and funds and the Smart Village Movement are the best options for improving or providing the above facilities.

Further literature review on various papers is shown in table 2.3 below.

Table 2.3: Literature Review

S.N.	Title of paper	Country	Characteristics and focused area	Published on /By	Year of Publication
1	“Smart Village A Sustainable Model for Community Development”	Bhutan	Smart Village model approach focused on agriculture along with technology transfer	Noppawan Boontham, Chomchuan Boonrahong, Sathaporn Sangsupoh and Surapol Dumronggittigule	2015
2	“Review on Development of Smart Villages”	India	The implementation of the smart village concept and the importance of digital transformation in rural areas	Prof. Shahid Arshad, Mohammad Mohsin, Rizwan Khan, Tanveer Khan, Twinkle Ramteke	2020
3	“Clean and Smart Village: Aspects and Alternatives”	India	Focus on water supply, sanitation, solid waste management development and implementation	Dr. Milind Kulkarni	2015
4	“Research on the Beijing rural villages’ classification & development under urbanization”	China	Village System Planning for sustainable development of rural areas.	Zhao Zhifeng	2009

5	“Building Smart Villages: A blueprint As piloted in Niger”	Nigeria	Broadband infrastructure improves internet access in rural areas and promotes rural digital development and transformation.	International Telecommunication Union(ITU)	2020
6	“Smart Villages Through Information Technology – Need of Emerging India”	India	Application of ICT and GIS for Smart village Development	Pinak Ranade , Sunil Londhe ,Asima Mishra	2015
7	“Smart village a case study of Kolavada Village”	India	Provide garbage disposal, sanitation facilities and other facilities to promote the development of the village and improve the standard of living and employment.	Bhagya Niranjanbhai Patel, Prof. Rinni Shah	2017
8	“Case Study Of Smart Village And Local Village”	India	Focus on improving the efficiency of resource use, local autonomy, and guaranteeing access to basic services	Kochare Akshay, Kendre Madhav, Anarse Prabhu, Bhoale Ajit, Prof. A.Tripathi	2019

9	“Study and development of village as a smart village”	India	Focus on resource efficiency, local self-government and ensuring basic needs	Rutuja Somwanshi, Utkarsha Shindepatil, Deepali Tule, Archana Mankar, Namdev Ingle Guided By- Dr. V. S. Rajamanya, Prof. A. Deshmukh	2016
10	“SMART VILLAGE DEVELOPMENT PRINCIPLES AND DRIVING FORCES: THE CASE OF LITHUANIA”	Lithuania	Smart Village development with public participation and LEADER approach	Vilma Atkočiūnienė , Gintarė Vaznonienė	2019
11	“Smart Village- The Real Future of India”	India	Education and benefit of Information and technology to local youth	Mrs. B. Josephine Sandhya Rani	2016
12	“SMART VILLAGES: New thinking for off-grid communities worldwide”	University of Cambridge, UK	Energy for the development and employment generation in the village	Brian Heap	2015

13	“Gender equity in access to and benefits from modern energy and improved energy technologies: World Development Report Background Paper”	USA	Improve women's quality of life through the use of improved energy technologies	Joy Clancy, Tanja Winther, Magi Matinga, and Sheila Oparaocha	2012
----	--	-----	---	---	------

2.3 Research Gap

As of Nepal Budget Speech (2015/2016), Nepal Government proposed three cities to develop as a smart city named Palungtar from Gorkha District, Lumbini from Rupandehi District and Nijghad from Bara District and also process of developing 12 smart cities throughout the country moved forward. The Government of Nepal has not developed any regulatory documents which can illustrate the requirements for smart villages but the local government has proposed the smart village concept as the percentage of villages in Nepal is higher. So it is beneficial to develop villages as a smart village rather than developing cities as smart. That is why the research is conducted with a view to analyze the international practice suitable in the Nepalese context and to assess the practicability of developing smart villages.

Chapter-3

METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study Area

Sandakpur Rural municipality is located in the eastern part of Nepal and is an exceptionally renowned tourist destination for trekking. The study area is famous for its cool weather, homestay, and Mai Pokhari. After the restructuring of the local bodies, Sandakpur Rural Municipality is formed by agglomeration of 5 existing Village Development Committees, namely Maimajhuwa, Mabu, Sulubung, Jamuna, and Maipokhari VDCs. Out of these VDCs, Maipokhari VDC is partially merged whereas other VDCs are completely merged to form Sandakpur Rural Municipality. The study will be limited only to some specific settlement areas or villages of the Maipokhari and Sulubung areas. The specific features of the study area are:

- Existing VDCs: Maipokhari, Sulubung VDCs
- Restructured Structure: Sandakpur Rural Municipality ward 1 and 3
- Area: 48.86 sq. km (Ward -1 and 3)
- Location: 27.01 N, 87.93 E
- No. of household:1374
- Population Details
 1. Male Population: 3027
 2. Female Population: 3220
 3. Total Population: 6247
 4. Population density: 127.85
 5. Average household size: 4

Figure 3.1: GIS Map of Study Area

3.1.1 Specific Location

- Specific project location: Maipokhari and Sulubung Area
- Expected serviceable household within the area: 45
- Expected immediate beneficiaries: 200 people
- Expected direct beneficiaries: 6247 people

Figure 3.2: Study Area (Source: Google Earth)

3.2 Research Approach

The philosophy of the research is pragmatism as it mostly focuses on the application of this research in the real world and the approach of research as a mixed method was applied because some data is collected in descriptive form, while other data is collected in numeric form. The strategy was adopted as a case study since a certain locality was chosen and data was collected within the locality through household interviews and a scheduled questionnaire and the analysis was done based on the collected data.

The quantitative approach has been used for the measurement of practicability assessment of smart village whereas the qualitative approach has been used to find the various factors suitable for smart village development.

3.3 Sampling and Population

In this study, the population is the total number of households in wards 1 and 3. Out of a total 45 households were taken as a sample from different locations forming the cluster of 15 each under the pandemic of COVID-19. A household interview and scheduled questionnaire were done to find the present status of the health, education, governance, services, water supply, irrigation in the area along with their perception of smart village practicability. Along with that, a Key Informant Interview (KII) was done with the local leaders and representatives of the hospital and

school. To locate the various components of the smart village and to know the present status of infrastructures, land use and features GPS survey was done which helped to prepare a GIS map.

Table3.1: Sampling Method

S.N.	Method	Total Sample	Respondents	Remark
1	Household Interviews and Scheduled Questionnaire	45	Household Representative	Cluster Sampling Method
2	Key Informant Interview	10	Local leaders, Hospital and School Representatives	Snowball Sampling Method
3	GPS Survey	-	Waypoint marking on features	GIS Map Preparation

3.4 Data Collection

The study relies on both the primary and secondary data:

3.4.1 Primary Data

Primary data were collected through household interviews, scheduled questionnaire surveys and Key Informant Interview (KII).

The data collection followed the concept of inclusivity and primary data related to different sectors of the society was collected by enumerators. The major sectors of the study were:

- Household Characteristics
- Land use and agriculture
- Social infrastructure (Sustainability, Equality, Security, Education, Health, and so forth)
- Economy
- Governance and public services
- Issues of environmental concern
- Access and Use of ICT infrastructure

3.4.2 Secondary Data

Recent and reliable baseline data were extracted by secondary sources like office records or documents, municipality reports, ward profiles, distributed scholarly or expert reports, and information distributed by the Central Bureau of Statistics (CBS) or other approved offices.

3.5 Analysis of Data

Analysis was done utilizing Excel/SPSS programming, spatial investigation utilizing GIS programming, for example, ArcGIS and so on, and translation of aeronautical photos, maps accessible of various periods. Significant programming and framework were utilized to investigate the ICT situation. In this part, the following significant examination was done for assessing the specific objective of the research:

A) The Idea of the Smart Village and Institutional Development

- a. Local-level enthusiasm and challenges for smart village,
- b. Local-level probability and need for ICT,
- c. Land use,
- d. Infrastructure improvement,
- e. Linkage of the proposed territory to local and national level,
- f. Reliability/Sufficiency,
- g. Sustainable Village and Communities,
- h. Public Information,
- i. Transparency and Accountability

B) Technical Development Indicator

- a. Clean Water and Sanitation,
- b. Affordable and Clean Energy,
- c. Quality Education,
- d. Good Health and Well-being

Practicability Assessment

To find the rank of the features of Smart Village, the **Likert scale** was used. The five-point scale ranged from one to five was adopted. Interpretation on Likert scale was done as:

Note:	Range for Five-Point Likert Scale
1=Excellent	1.00-1.80
2=Good	1.90-2.60
3=Fair	2.70-3.40
4=Poor	3.50-4.20
5=Very Poor	4.30-5.00

Average= (Sum of Opinion/Number of Respondents)

Testing of Hypothesis

The hypothesis test was carried out with the establishment of the null hypothesis and the alternative hypothesis and to determine the significance of respondent's opinions for the variables from the collected data, a non-parametric test, the **Chi-square test** was conducted.

It is calculated as,

$$\chi^2 = \sum \frac{(O-E)^2}{E}$$

Where,

χ^2 = Chi-Squared

O = Observed Frequency

E = Expected Frequency

Null Hypothesis. $H_0: \mu_1 = \mu_2$ i.e. There is no significant difference between the opinion of respondents.

Alternative Hypothesis. $H_1: \mu_1 \neq \mu_2$ i.e. There is a significant difference between the opinions of respondents.

C) Economic Feasibility Indicator

The economic feasibility of any project provides the investor with a decisive idea about investing in the project and the pattern of return of his investment. The basics of economic analysis for the selection of projects include the net present value of the project, its benefit-cost ratio, payback period, internal rate of return, breakeven point. In 1848 Jules Dupuit developed the concept of economic analysis for flood management projects.

In this research, we use cost-benefit analysis, NPV and IRR to determine whether a smart village is feasible or not.

Let us assume the discount rate as 6.5 % as of *Nepal Rastra Bank* and 10% due to fluctuations in the cost of capital due to pandemic of COVID-19 and other various reasons and the total analysis period be 30 years.

1. Benefit-Cost Ratio Formula

The benefit-cost ratio provides the measure of benefit with respect to cost at a definite time frame. It is the measure of benefit if the total cost is unit. "Cost-benefit analysis (CBA) estimates and summarizes the monetary value of the benefits and costs of the project community, and then draws

a conclusion about whether they are worthwhile. These projects can be highways, training programs, health systems and so forth” (Gupta, 2009). For the acceptance of the project, the B/C ratio should be greater than unity.

$$\text{Modified B/C ratio} = \frac{\text{Total benefit after discounting operating expenses}}{\text{Initial Investment after discounting salvage value}}$$

Cost-Benefit Analysis Process

1. Set the framework.

It is all the aspects and scope of the project.

2. Identify benefits and costs.

Costs in the smart village include capital cost, operation cost, maintenance cost and other costs. For the cyber security in smart village, cyber security cost is very important. The benefit includes reduced travel time, less fuel and energy consumption, improved safety, reduced gas emission, greenhouse gases, and economic impact.

3. Assessment of different variables within the lifetime of the smart village.

Within the assumed lifetime of any project, various variables may appear. In this step, the characteristics and frequency of the project variables are projected.

4. Calculation of the discount costs and benefits to obtain present values and calculation of benefit-cost ratio: In this step, all the discounted costs and benefits are calculated to obtain the benefit-cost ratio with the given formula.

2. Net present value (NPV)

Net present value is the total worth of the project at the present time. It is calculated by discounting all cash flows to the present time with an interest rate equal to the Minimum Attractive Rate of Return (MARR).

The project is accepted if its net present value is positive.

$$\text{Net Present Value (NPV)} = \frac{A((1+i)^n - 1)}{i(1+i)}$$

Where,

A = Net annual revenue

n= Time Period

i = MARR

3. Internal Rate of Return(IRR)

The IRR is actually the capital budgeting technique that equates the response of the NPV to the initial investment or cost.

The project is accepted if

- If IRR > i, accept the project.
- If IRR < i, reject the project.
- If IRR = i, accept the project

It is calculated as:

$$0 = \text{NPV} = \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{CF}{(1+IRR)^n} - CF_0$$

Where:

CF=Net cash inflow during the period

CF_0 =Total initial investment costs

IRR= Internal Rate of Return

i = MARR

n=Time Period

3.6 Framework and Flowchart for the Study

Deductive logical reasoning was adopted including a progression of techno-political exercises which got to the current circumstance of frameworks, economy, administration, and way of life of individuals and contrast it and the set principles, which decide the potential intercessions and figure a drawn-out vision for the improvement of the zone with respect to the rationale of the project. The conceptual framework and flowchart for the study process is shown in the figure 3.3 below:

Figure 3.3: Framework and Flowchart for the Study

Literature Review is a continuous process for the research.

3.7 Summary of Research Methodology

The summary of the Research Methodology is shown in table 3.1 below.

Table 3.1: Summary of Research Methodology

S.N.	Objective	Source of Information	Analysis and Interpretation
1	To develop an idea of the smart village with an institutional development plan and its integral features/attributes in the Nepalese context each for countrywide and local level via a literature assessment of worldwide practice centred on developing countries.	Existing Documents, Reports, Extensive Literature review, Key Informant Interview	Content Analysis
2	To analyse the technological advancement needed for the progression of the smart village with a case of Sandakpur Rural Municipality.	Household Survey, Key Informant Interview, Scheduled Questionnaire	Descriptive Analysis, Likert Scale, Chi-Square Test
3	To assess economic feasibility for the advancement as a smart village with a case of Sandakpur Rural Municipality.	Forecasting of development cost and operating cost of smart village	Cost-Benefit Assessment, NPV, IRR

Chapter-4

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

4.1 Idea of Smart Village

After the literature review of different research of smart villages in the world, some of the characteristics are adopted which suited the study area and the theme of the topic.

4.1.1 Features of Smart Village

A. Smart Utilization of Resources

For the upliftment of villages use of resources should be done in a well-organized manner. As agriculture is one of the main sources of income generation in the rural community. It is the most adopted employment by rural dwellers. Through the process of technology transfer and use of modern technologies like drip and sprinkler irrigation productivity can be increased. Natural resources and human resources available there, with their proper utilization, contribute to the development of villages.

Pollution of the environment can be reduced by the use of natural resources and a friendly environment can be achieved by plantation (Rutuja, 2016). “It is necessary to evaluate the performance of technology transfer to the community economy to consider important indicators consisting of progress, efficiency, effectiveness, impact, relevance, sustainability and equity” (Boontham,2015).

Smart Utilization of Resources is the key to a sustainable country, so many countries are using biological calculators, ecological calculators to make a balance between consumption and production of resources. During the questionnaire survey, it was found that the people here are mostly dependent on natural resources, agriculture, medicinal herbs and livestock. They are generating income with the natural resource available i.e. tourists are attracted here because of the pleasant environment and natural beauty.

B. Smart Living

Smart life is defined as the use of technology & the interest in things to pursuit a more efficient, controllable & productive lifestyle. Use of recent technologies in the field of ICT along with better fundamental needs like fresh and good food, safe and clean drinking water, better sanitation, environmental protection, digester management and security. Not only are these enough, facilities like well-managed roads, sports areas and parks, banking are also the necessity of smart living.

For both rural and urban areas, smart villages are needed to improve livelihoods and technology. In urban areas, livelihoods are affected by the migration from rural areas, because urban areas already have technical support (A.Shahid, 2020).

Smart living changes the dimension of life with the improvement in lifestyle, environment and awareness. During KII it was found that the lifestyle of the people must be changed and the village

lacks most of the facilities like health, better educational institutes, sanitation, well-managed roads, etc. which are the basic requirements for smart living. Infrastructure and awareness are needed which can change the lifestyle of the village.

C. Smart Governance

Smart Villages relies on good governance, such as openness (i.e., transparency), accountability, collaboration (i.e., involving all stakeholders), and participatory (i.e., citizens' participation) principles and on Electronic Government (e-Government) which sustains the smart village. To maintain transparency and public participation there is a need of smart governance.

Involvement of local people in local development plans and use local and appropriate tools to transform the foregoing activities into possible actions. Regular and punctual attendance of government employees, timely provision of services, and provision of online services in various departments are some of the characteristics of intelligent governance (Rutuja, 2016).

With the formation of local government local people are getting services a bit fast and efficiently but during the survey, it was found that upgrading of infrastructures and manpower was the prime need of the village.

D. Smart Village Services

Essential services like health, education, and transportation along with economic services like job availability, entrepreneurship, and site for economic activities like shops, markets, etc. are required in the smart village.

Only by promoting the integrated development of urban and rural areas can we speed up rural construction; combine land development with industrial development; cluster these villages; and establish infrastructure and facility networks for each village cluster (Zhifeng, 2009).

When people become smart, definitely the surroundings they live on becomes smart. During the survey, the village services which are needed for the day-to-day life were found to lack well-equipped infrastructures and services provided by them were not sufficient to sustain in the village.

E. Smart Technology

To develop the village as a smart village internet availability is the most. For that development and construction of IT infrastructure is most which can further develop appropriate rural technologies.

The use of IT in rural areas helps rural communities develop social innovation and sustainable housing development. Social innovation and organizational culture in rural areas is a self-discipline mechanism of local communities, which helps to monitor compliance with the principles of the smart village (Atkočiūnienė, 2019).

The knowledge of new and productive tools which make life easy are technologies. During KII it was found that most people use a mobile phone, schools were not able to provide computer education, there was no equipment in the health post and the recent technologies used in the field of agriculture were not seen. So there was a need for modern agriculture equipment, tools recent technologies in the health sector, awareness and education

F. Smart Tourism

To increase the productivity and lifestyle of rural dwellers tourism is the most important factor. It flourishes the identity of the village at a national and global level. The village can further enhance and share their culture and tradition and attract tourists as a new tourist destination.

“In order to make rural tourism sustainable and promote it through the concept of sustainability, specific goals should focus on receiving a high-quality low number of tourists rather than a low quality-high number” (Thapa, 2010).

Tourism can change the prospectus of the village and the country. During the survey, it was found that the village has the possibility of tourism but it lacked well-equipped hotels, homestays, roads, and other infrastructure. The implementation of smart tourism, adventure tourism, accessible tourism, and agritourism can change the lifestyle of the village.

G. Gender Equity and Women Empowerment

Gender equality recognizes that women and men have different needs and interests and need to redistribute power and resources to achieve equality in life outcomes (Reeves and Baden, 2000).

Self-esteem and self-confidence can only be achieved by women who are financially empowered. This is a way for others to see them as equal members of society. Women play an important role in the development of the family and the country as a whole (Rutuja, 2016).

During The survey, it was found that children in the village are getting their primary education, women have participated in local government, and some are doing their own occupation. *Chaupadi Pratha*, which is a tradition that banishes females during menstruation is absent here which shows their condition is not worst. But the problem of child marriage was seen which hampered mostly girls' education which results in a female literacy rate of 69.11% which is lower than the male literacy rate of 82.21% according to census report 2011. Although women were self-empowered they were still dominated in society.

4.1.2 Institutional Development Plan

In order for every city or village to develop, it needs institutions that are vital to sustainable and beneficial economic growth. Institutions formulate guidelines, mobilize and manage resources, and provide services to stimulate and sustain development. If the institutions they operate are dysfunctional, growth and prosperity cannot be sustained (McGill, 1996).

Goal and Strategy of Institutional Development

1. Smart and Dynamic Governance

To promote sustainable development and enhance resident's capacity to address the environmental and development issues local government plays an important role. For the government to be smart and dynamic it should possess characteristics like efficiency, transparency, social integration, effectiveness, continuous improvement with improved and advance use of modern technology and communication. The most important aspects of smart governance are E-governance and the involvement of the public in the decision-making process.

2. Ensure Public Participation

When public concerns, needs, and values are incorporated into government and corporate decision-making, this is called public participation. The primary goal of public participation is better public support for decision-making, followed by two-way communication and interaction (James L., 2005).

In Nepal, the concept of public participation was visualized in the Local Self Governance Act 1999. Formation of local bodies and providing them with the power to establish the civil society based on a democratic process with transparency and accountability along with public participation was its main motto. The legislative provision of public participation was disrupted locally due to uncertainty of local election until 2016. Until 2016 the central government was only the body that continuously reformed the structure and processes of public participation so that people can participate in the local policy-making process. After the formation of local bodies in Nepal, with the increase in policy-making power, public participation became successful to some extent.

3. Ensure Local Legislation with Economic and Sustainable Development

Local legislation means the power of the local body to make its own rules and regulation and formulate and maintain within its boundary. After the formation of local government in Nepal, they make their own rule and regulation without crossing the limit of the constitution of Nepal which ensures the availability of relevant ordinances in support of social, economic development, and environmental management.

With the formation of local government, it prioritized areas with pronounced needs or inadequate services and areas that benefit the greater majority also identify areas of great economic potentials.

Activities for Institutional Development

1. Development of e-municipal service system and related training and awareness programs.
2. Promotion and adaptation of e-procurement system.
3. Implementation of bylaws and building code.
4. Promotion of Gender Equality and Social Inclusion (GESI) in municipal organizational structure.
5. Promotion & Development of the public-private partnership.
6. Construction of digital information boards in each ward office.

Smart Village can only be successful if there is good coordination between three levels of government i.e. local, state and central.

4.2 Technological Development Plan

Smart Villages are the need of the present scenario of the world as development is needed for both rural and urban areas for better livelihood and Information technology will offer effective solutions. Geoinformatics helps to transform villages into smart villages because it can represent an important step towards the use and implementation of ICT in “smart villages” in terms of decision support systems. In order to support innovative solutions for management, governance and citizen participation practices that meet the goals of smart villages, recently developed technologies such as GIS, GPS, remote sensing, web services, and location-based services and technologies may be the best choice. Other than these some basic technologies most for smart villages are:

- a. ICT Infrastructures like the construction of network towers, an extension of fibre optics cable for communication and internet, public Wi-Fi, website and app of the village with regular update and control center of ICT services.
- b. Well maintained road with a drainage system, street light, Bus Park, market and park for refreshment.
- c. School and college with ICT facility.
- d. Health center with well-equipped instruments, ambulance, and manpower.
- e. Construction of Reservoir tank with treatment plant, manpower, and public stand post.
- f. The solar home system, biogas as cooking fuel, improved cooking stove, etc.
- g. Installation of devices for weather monitoring and training for the disaster management team.
- h. Use of handy agriculture tools like hand tractors for ploughing, sprinkler irrigation, and drip irrigation where water quantity is less.
- i. Solid Waste collection vehicles and solid waste treatment setup.
- j. Construction of public toilets with the sewerage system.
- k. Retrofitting of old houses and construction of the new house as earthquake resistance.

1. Construction of area police station and installation of a security camera at the prime junction.

The study area is located in Sandakpur Rural Municipality named Maipokhari and Sulubung village in Ilam district of Province 1, Nepal. It is approximately 13 km away from Ilam Bazar. The selection of the village is that it lies in the tourism loop on the way to the famous Sandakphur and also has a famous religious and tourist spot named Maipokhari. The area has a moderate climate prevailing the highest average temperature of 26°C in June and the lowest is 16°C in January. There is a lot of rainfall in summer & in the winter it is quite dry again. There is about 1157mm rain in a year.

4.2.1 Demography

According to Population Census 2011, Sandakpur Rural Municipality has a population of 16,065 with 3643 households. From the village Ward Profile of Sandakpur Rural Municipality Population of different wards is shown below.

Table 4.1: Population Distribution

Ward	Year	Total Population	Male Population	Female Population	Others	Density(/km ²)
1	2020	2848	1497	1351	2	82.59
2	2020	2858	1530	1328	-	61.06
3	2020	3032	1506	1526	-	208.09
4	2020	3464	1798	1665	1	118.22
5	2020	3324	1719	1604	1	107.85
TOTAL		15528	8050	7474	4	

(Source: Sandakpur Rural Municipality Profile)

Ethnicity

Rai, Limbu, Brahmin, Chhetri, Tamang, Magar, Sherpa

Festivals

Chandi Nach, Dhaan Nach, Buddha Purnima, Dashain, Tihar, Lhosar

Important Markets

Deurali Bazzar, Maimajhuwa, Mabu, Jaubari

Tourist Centers

Sandakpur Danda, Mai Temple, Kaal Pokhari, Dhapp Pokhari, Maipokhari Lake, Todke Fall, Jaubari Bazar, Deurali Bazar, Dhappar Falls, Mabutham Viewpoint, Pahakhola falls, Upper Mai Hydropower, Hangetham, Bird Eye Place

Now focusing on the study area of wards 1 and 3, no roads are belonging to the Strategic Road Network (SRN) in the study area. The study area is linked with the national road network at Barbote of Mechi Highway by a district road 03DR011 (Barbote-Mai Pokhari-Budhabare-Goruwale-Sandakpur Road). Further, another link to the study area with the Mechi Highway is 03DR012 (Barbote-Sumbek-Sulubung-Mai Khola-Mabu, Kalpokhari Road). But the condition of these roads is very poor as it is not even gravelled and it runs out of service during the rainy season. Recently 3 km out of 13km road from Barbote at Mechi Highway to Maipokhari has been all-weather blacktopped and around 6 km out of 13 km has been widened.

4.2.2 Agriculture and Land Use

Sandakpur has ample scope for agriculture and agro-based industry. According to the SRM profile data 2020, 92% of the population is dependent on agriculture and only 46% of the farmers' land has access to irrigation. The remaining more than 50% doesn't have such access & should largely depend upon rainwater.

Some of the major agricultural products having a high scope of production are firmly explained below:

a. Medicinal herbs like:

Satuwa, Mojito Indreni, Lauth Salla, Sunkhari, Chiraito, Panch Aanule, Kudki, Okkhe Aalu, Chimfing are grown by farmers. These plants have high market scope in the medicinal herb industry. As reported in the ground, there is the presence of a medicinal herb storage center and the necessity of a medicinal herb processing center.

b. Under Prime Minister Agriculture Modernization Project (PMAMP) there is Kiwi Zone in Sandakpur. So ample scope for kiwi farming. In interaction with the people involved in farming, they reported an annual profit gain of 2-3 lakhs.

Lack of post-harvesting storage and custom hiring remains a hurdle for further development of kiwi farming.

c. Milk and dairy products production and livestock rearing are other aspects of agriculture that can be flourished.

- d. Although agriculture is the basic occupation of residents of the study area, no step has been taken for the modernization of agricultural practice. The area is suitable for the production of cash crops like cardamom, potato, and broom grass 'amliso'. But due to a lack of proper marketing strategy and management of produced products, the farmers are not getting the return from those activities.

The land use map of Sandakpur Rural Municipality is shown below in figure 4.1 which indicates the forest resource available and extensive agricultural land with clustered settlements or built-up areas.

Figure 4.1: Location of Municipality with Land Cover

4.2.3. Existing Condition of Village

The scheduled questionnaire survey and key informant interview (From Annex A and Annex B) which describes the present scenario of the village is shown below:

Table 4.2: Questionnaire and Responses

S.N.	Questionnaire	Response(In percentage)	
1	Literate Member in the Family.	All = 22.5%	More Than 50% =77.8%
2	Primary Education of Children.	Goes to School=91.1%	Doesn't go to school=8.9%
3	Financially Active Female Members in the Family.	Yes= 66.7%	No = 33.3%
4	Income is enough to fulfil basic needs within the year.	Yes=93.2%	No=6.8%
5	Earthquake Resistant House.	Yes= 62.2%	No= 37.8%
6	Risk of Landslide.	Yes= 22.2%	No = 77.8%
7	Road Type	Earthen=55.6%	Gravel=44.4%
8	Water Supply to the House.	Directly to the House=88.6%	Have to go to Nearby Stand Post=11.4%
9	Drainage and Rain Water Management System.	Yes= 75.6%	No = 24.4%
10	Toilet and its Condition.	Well Managed Toilet=88.9%	Simple Toilet=11.1%
11	Transparency of Information by municipality office.	Provide Information=68.9%	Doesn't Provide Information = 31.1%
12	Participation in the group in the development work of the village.	Yes=71.1%	No=28.9%
13	Use of Mobile Internet.	Yes=80%	No=20%
14	Use of Mobile Banking.	Yes=60%	No=40%
15	Use of Wi-Fi at Home.	Yes=80%	No=20%
16	Use of Electricity	Yes=100%	No=0%

17	Safety of the living area	Safe=63.6%	Sporadic Events =36.4%
18	In Search of Employment in the Village.	Work In the Village Premises =82.2%	Work outside of the Village=17.8%

Further obtained results in the village are described in the form of charts as below:

A. Main Source of Income

From the chart, it is clear that agriculture is the dominating source of income generation and after that, the hotel industry is the next. So, to develop the village as a smart village, implementation of smartness in agriculture is most. With the improvement in the agriculture sector, with proper market and technology, it can only be possible to improve the lifestyle of the village. As of the census report of Nepal, 2011 66% of the population is directly engaged in farming and according to the SRM profile, 92% of the total population is dependent on agriculture. Also from the survey, 70% of households are directly and indirectly engaged in agriculture. So, keeping in mind the excess chance of agriculture flourishment & too with a moto of smart farming focus should be given for the development of this sector from all beneficiaries who are benefited directly or indirectly

Figure 4.2: Main Source of Income generation

B. Housing Condition

Due to harder geographic conditions & transportation, as well as climatic factors and not abundant availability & costly rate of RCC building construction, most of the building is wood & CGI constructed structure. RCC structured buildings are in limited number and few were seen in the market area. According to the SRM profile data, more than 80% of houses are constituting CGI sheet construction

Figure 4.3: Housing Condition

C. Fuel for Cooking

Liquefied petroleum gas is available easily within the market area but due to the ease in availability of firewood people here use both sources of fuel for cooking purposes. But due to the use of firewood as a source of fuel, most old age people are suffering from lung problems. About 90% of Nepal population is dependent on biomass and less than 5% of rural dwellers use LPG gas (KC, Surendra,2011). So, the data shows that LPG gas is dominating the firewood as the source of fuel.

Figure 4.4: Fuel for Cooking

D Education and IT

There are 33 schools throughout the SRM but none are providing higher education. Some schools are providing computer education to the students but most of the families don't know whether their children use computers and the internet at school. According to SRM data, 53% of the total population are literate which is below the literacy rate of Nepal i.e. 66% according to census report 2011. So improvement in the education system is the most in the village.

Figure 4.5: Education and IT

E. Health Service

SRM have altogether seven health post but lacks hospital with a higher level of service. The services provided by the health post are basic and they have to go to the nearby municipality if the case is very serious. With such infrastructure development health service of the rural municipality is believed to be developed in the upcoming future.

Figure 4.6: Health Service

After the survey of the village, the location of components necessary in the village is shown in the GIS map below in figure 4.7:

SMART VILLAGE COMPONENTS

Location Map

Legend

Figure 4.7: GIS Map of Proposed Components Location

4.2.4 Practicability Status of Sandakpur Municipality

Data were collected throughout the study area to know the present status of the village concerning the smart village components and their characteristics. The data was collected as Yes/No to know the basic status of people and also Likert Scale was also used to know the opinion of people towards the smart village characteristics in the present scenario. The following table 4.3 shows the number of respondents and the interpretation of their opinion (From Annex A).

Table 4.3: Likert Scale Table

Number of Respondents/Variabes	Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor	Very Poor	Average	Interpretation
Smart Utilization of Resources	0	14	26	4	1	2.82	Fair
Smart Living	1	10	23	9	2	3.02	Fair
Smart Governance	1	11	24	8	1	2.93	Fair
Smart Village Services	0	6	26	12	1	3.17	Fair
Smart Technology	0	6	27	9	3	3.2	Fair
Smart Tourism	10	10	21	4	0	2.42	Good
Gender Equity and Women Empowerment	0	2	25	13	5	3.46	Poor

Note:

Interpretation Range for Five-Point Likert Scale

1=Excellent 1.00-1.80

2=Good 1.90-2.60

3=Fair 2.70-3.40

4=Poor 3.50-4.20

5=Very Poor 4.30-5.00

Average= (Sum of Opinion/Number of Respondents)

Figure 4.8: Likert Scale Chart Showing Percentage of Respondents

From table 4.3 and chart, it is very clear that at present in the village, resource utilization and their living are just fair and they are getting services from the government not in well managed but in a decent way. The village economy is dependent on agriculture and tourism and is giving more priority to infrastructures for tourism but the village is still behind the recent technologies that urban people utilize. Every feature needed for a smart village is on the way to improve but the women were found still backward from the surveyed data.

To determine the significance of respondent’s opinions for the variables from the collected data, a non-parametric test, the **Chi-Square test** was conducted with a 5% level of significance. Table 4.4 shows the result of the Chi-square test (From Annex C).

Table 4.4: Result of Chi-Square Test

Statement	Chi-Square p-value	Result
<p><u>Null Hypothesis.</u> $H_0: \mu_1=\mu_2$ i.e. There is no significant difference between the opinion of respondents.</p> <p><u>Alternative Hypothesis.</u> $H_1: \mu_1\neq\mu_2$ i.e. There is a significant difference between the opinions of respondents.</p>	1.39577E-07	1.39577E-07<0.05, H_1 is accepted

Since the calculated value of the Chi-square p-value is less than 0.05, alternate hypothesis H_1 is accepted. Therefore, there is a significant difference between the opinions of respondents. Hence, every respondent has a different opinion, the priority is given to the dominating value i.e. from above table 4.3, the majority of respondents supported the perspective toward smart village features as fair.

4.2.5 Challenge for Smart Village Transformation

Land Acquisition

The primary hazard in the implementation of Smart Village at any place is the availability of land for the establishment of infrastructure (i.e. Physical, Social and Environmental). So provisions relating to land availability should be made clear before the commencement of the project. For this few models of land acquisition are proposed in this report.

Acquiring Land via Upper Ceiling of Land (*Jagga Hadbandi*)

As Per chapter 3 of the Land Act 2021: Land can be acquired from people owing lands higher than the upper ceiling of land allowed by the Land Act 2021. As per clause 7, Chapter 3 of the Land acquisition act, the upper Ceiling of land that can be owned by any person is 10 *Bigaha* for *terai*, 25 *Ropani* for Kathmandu Valley and 70 *Ropani* for all hilly regions except Kathmandu Valley. Apart from this for housing purposes further 1 *Bigaha* in *Terai*, 5 *Ropani* in Kathmandu Valley and all hilly regions can be owned. Acquisition of land above Upper Ceiling can be an effective way of acquiring land required for the establishment of Smart Village in the Hilly region. The detailed process of Acquisition of Land over Upper Ceiling is dealt with in Chapter 4 of Land act 2021(1964 A.D).

Acquisition of Land for Public Purpose Subjected to Compensation

As per section 3 of the Land acquisition act 2034, if the Nepalese government deems it necessary, it may requisition land for public purposes at any location, subject to compensation in accordance with this law.

So, the lands required for the construction of infrastructure may be acquired by the government from the public by giving appropriate compensation. The process of acquisition of land as per the act is briefly explained below along with proper sections of the act. If any further detailing regarding the acquisition process is required then the land acquisition act, 2034 may be referred. Section 6,7,8,9 and 10 of the Land acquisition act describes the details of the acquisition process.

Site-Specific Analysis

The land ownership pattern in the Sandakpur area is of mixed type. The existing land plots are owned by the public as well as the government. So about the acquisition of land for establishing an infrastructure of smart Village, the following measures are proposed:

- For small patches of private property that are adjacent to the existing public lands, it should be acquired by the government subjected to compensation to the property holders.
- For comparatively bigger plots of private land, the government should negotiate with the property holder to hand over 40% of the land to the government leaving 60% of it to the owner. In such a case, the government shall invest and build infrastructure in the donated property and the original owner shall enjoy any sort of benefit from the constructed infrastructure but ownership shall be retained by the government.
- For large plots of private land, the provision of the upper ceiling of land should be implemented/ and the property which has not been in any purpose for a long time should be acquired by the government and should be brought into use.
- For plots of land which are owned by a definite beneficiary group such as community forests amid the area proposed for the purpose, the government should acquire the land along with compensation by allotting another land in exchange. In this case, public infrastructure in the acquired plot and its operation rights should be transferred to the beneficiary group.
- For extreme cases where the land or property is owned by a certain beneficiary group, the government should obtain the property on lease.

4.3 Economic Feasibility of Smart Village

For the strategic planning for the development of Smart Village at Sandakpur the most prominent prospect of the area (i.e. tourism) should be focused and all the interventions land infrastructure development plans should be developed by keeping tourism in the center. The assumed cost is shown in table 4.5:

Table 4.5: Assumed Cost

S.N.	Description of Work	Quantity	Unit	Rate	Amount(Rs)	Duration	Financing Agencies	Remarks
1	Blacktopping of approach road to Mechi Highway for smooth traffic	13	Km	5700000	74,100,000.00	10yr	Central / donor agencies	
2	Bus Park	1	Job	3000000	30,00,000.00	20yr	Provincial government	
3	Blacktopping 4 km around market area	4	km	5700000	22,800,000.00	20yr	Provincial government	
4	Arrangement of public transportation	4	Nos	-	20,000,000.00	20yr	Municipal / provincial govt.	
5	Gravelling of other roads within the smart village (periodic maintenance)	12	Km	2500000	30,000,000.00	20yr	Municipal / provincial govt.	
6	Area Water Supply Scheme and irrigation	2	Nos	-	58,200,000	20yr	Municipal/ provincial government	Construction of 100cum RVT and overall system

7	Public Toilets, and Solid waste management	-	-	-	12,500,000.00	20yr	Central government / donor agencies	Dumping site is also included
8	Extension of fibre optics cable for Telephone Line and internet services from Mechi Highway to the proposed village	13	km	345000	4,485,000.00	5yr	Network Company/ Provincial govt.	
9	Public Wi-Fi Spot and CCTV (at Bus station, Park, executive office, etc.)	20	Set	50000	1,000,000.00	5yr	Municipality	
10	Extension of fiber optics cable for Telephone Line and internet services within the smart village	10	km	345000	3,450,000.00	5yr	Network Company/ Provincial govt.	

11	Construction of Control central for overall facility	1	Nos	2500000	2,500,000.00	5yr	Municipality	
12	Single Pole Solar Street light (30 watt)	100	Nos	75000	7,500,000.00	5yr	Municipality	
13	Setup of bio gas technology for cooking fuel (six cum) and smokeless stove	50	Nos	80000	4,000,000.00	20yr	Central government / donor agencies	
14	Upgrading Higher Secondary School into college (Bachelor Program)	1	Job	3000000	3,000,000.00	10yr	Central government / donor agencies	
15	Upgrading Hospital with important and necessary medical equipment	-	-	-	50,000,000.00	20yr	Central government / donor agencies	

16	E-Library and ICT facility in Schools	1	Job	5000000	5,000,000.00	10yr	Central government / donor agencies	
17	Construction of Upgraded Homestays with better facilities	25	No	2000000	50,000,000.00	20yr	Central government / donor agencies	
18	Construction of Micro Agro Based Industry	3	No	10000000	30,000,000.00	20yr	Central government / donor agencies	
19	Total Cost				378,535,000.00			
20	Operation and Maintenance				500000/year till 5year and after that 1000000/year			

Assumed Benefit Could Be:

1. Travel Cost

House hold size of study area =1374

With The improvement of roads, they may use public bus service and own vehicle for traveling purpose.

Assume 50% use their own vehicles=687

Assume 50% use public vehicle= 687

Assuming these households generate 52 trips /year traveling to the local market or nearest Highway and cost per 1 km is Rs12. Then, for having their own vehicle=687*52*1*12=Rs428688/km/year

Travelling in Public Vehicle at Rs15/Km=687*52*1*15=Rs535, 860/km/year

Total Benefit=Rs964, 548/km/year

Assume the Average Distance Travelled by one household is 25 km/year. Then,

Total Benefit=25*964848=Rs.24, 113,700/year

2. Vehicle Tax and Toll

With the increase in the number of vehicle revenue on tax and toll also increases.

If 50% household have Private Vehicle, Then= $687*4000$ (Average Tax per year) =Rs2, 748,000/year

For Public Vehicles=Assume ADT of 100 Vehicles, Then= $100*50*365$ =Rs1, 825,000/year

Here, Rs50 is assumed as a Toll per 1 Vehicle.

Total Benefit= $2474800+1825000$ =Rs4, 299,800

3. Annual Tax Revenue

$1374*2000$ (Average Tax per year) =Rs2, 748,000/year

4. Agriculture Products Export

Rs17, 500,000

5. Tourism and Market

20,000,000/year

6. Medical Herbs

20,000,000/year

7. Fuel and Carbon Consumption Cost

1,000,000/year

8. Tax From School, College and Hospital

2,000,000/year

9. Other Benefits from electricity, internet, etc.

Rs3, 000,000

Total

Benefit= $24113700+4299800+2748000+17500000+20000000+20000000+1000000+2000000+3000000$ =**Rs94, 661,500/Year**

Let us assume Benefit starts from 5year and increases each year at the rate of 5% till 12year, 8% till 20year and 10 % after that till 30year.

Discount Rate as of *Nepal Rastra Bank*=6.5%

Let us also assume the discount rate as 10% due to fluctuations in the cost of capital due to the pandemic of COVID-19 and other various reasons and the total analysis period be 30 years. Calculation of B/C Ratio, NPV and IRR is shown in table 4.6 below.

4.3.1 B/C Ratio, NPV and IRR Analysis

Calculation of B/C Ratio, NPV and IRR is shown in table 4.6 below.

Table 4.6: B/C Ratio, NPV and IRR Analysis

Year	Cost(Rs)	Benefit(Rs)	Total Benefit	Discount Factor		Disc. Cost	Disc. Benefit	Disc. Cost	Disc. Benefit
				6.50%	10%				
0	378535000	0	-378535000	1	1	378535000	0	378535000	0
1	500000	0	-500000	0.938967	0.909091	469483.568	0	454545.45	0
2	500000	0	-500000	0.881659	0.826446	440829.641	0	413223.14	0
3	500000	0	-500000	0.827849	0.751315	413924.546	0	375657.4	0
4	500000	0	-500000	0.777323	0.683013	388661.545	0	341506.73	0
5	500000	9466150	94161500	0.729881	0.620921	364940.418	69091614.81	310460.66	58777343.82
6	100000	99394575	98394575	0.685334	0.564474	685334.119	68118493.47	564473.93	56105646.38
7	100000	104364303.8	103364303.8	0.643506	0.513158	643506.215	67159078.07	513158.12	53555389.72
8	100000	109582518.9	108582518.9	0.604231	0.466507	604231.188	66213175.56	466507.38	51121053.83
9	100000	115061644.9	114061644.9	0.567353	0.424098	567353.228	65280595.62	424097.62	48797369.56
10	100000	120814727.1	119814727.1	0.532726	0.385543	532726.036	64361150.62	385543.29	46579307.31
11	100000	126855463.5	125855463.5	0.500212	0.350494	500212.24	63454655.54	350493.9	44462066.07
12	100000	137003900.6	136003900.6	0.469683	0.318631	469682.854	64348383.08	318630.82	43653664.87
13	100000	147964212.6	146964212.6	0.441017	0.289664	441016.765	65254698.33	289664.38	42859961.87
14	100000	159801349.6	158801349.6	0.414104	0.263331	414100.249	66173778.59	263331.25	42080689.83
15	100000	172585457.6	171585457.6	0.388827	0.239392	388826.524	67105803.64	239392.05	41315586.38
16	100000	186392294.2	185392294.2	0.365095	0.217629	365095.328	68050955.81	217629.14	40564393.9
17	100000	201303677.7	200303677.7	0.342813	0.197845	342812.515	69009419.97	197844.67	39826859.47
18	100000	217407971.9	216407971.9	0.32189	0.179859	321889.685	69981383.63	179858.79	39102734.75
19	100000	234800609.7	233800609.7	0.302244	0.163508	302243.836	70967036.93	163507.99	38391775.94

20	100000 0	2535846 58.5	252584 658.5	0.2837 97	0.148 644	283797 .029	7196657 2.66	148643 .63	3769374 3.65
21	100000 0	2789431 24.3	277943 124.3	0.2664 76	0.135 131	266476 .083	7433167 1.29	135130 .57	3769374 3.65
22	100000 0	3068374 36.8	305837 436.8	0.2502 12	0.122 846	250212 .285	7677449 6.17	122845 .97	3769374 3.65
23	100000 0	3375211 80.4	336521 180.4	0.2349 41	0.111 678	234941 .113	7929760 1.67	111678 .16	3769374 3.65
24	100000 0	3712732 98.5	370273 298.5	0.2206 02	0.101 526	220601 .984	8190362 6.14	101525 .6	3769374 3.65
25	100000 0	4084006 28.3	407400 628.3	0.2071 38	0.092 296	207138 .013	8459529 4.61	92295. 998	3769374 3.65
26	100000 0	4492406 91.2	448240 691.2	0.1944 96	0.083 905	194495 .787	8737542 1.66	83905. 453	3769374 3.65
27	100000 0	4941647 60.3	493164 760.3	0.1826 25	0.076 278	182625 .152	9024691 4.39	76277. 684	3769374 3.65
28	100000 0	5435812 36.3	542581 236.3	0.1714 79	0.069 343	171479 .016	9321277 5.43	69343. 349	3769374 3.65
29	100000 0	5979393 59.9	596939 359.9	0.1610 13	0.063 039	161013 .16	9627610 6.08	63039. 409	3769374 3.65
30	100000 0	6577332 95.9	656733 295.9	0.1511 86	0.057 309	151186 .066	9944010 9.56	57308. 553	3769374 3.65
Total						389515 836	1939990 813	386066 521	1101825 024
						NPV	1550474 977		7157585 02.7
						Benefit/ Cost	4.98051 8462		2.85397 7135
						IRR	18.32%		

Hereafter benefit-cost ratio, Smart Village is cost-efficient as of assumed values. The benefit-cost ratio is 4.98 at a 6.5% discount rate and 2.85 at a 10% discount rate for a 30 year analysis period. With the benefit-cost ratio of **4.98** and **2.85** which is above one, it means the project benefit outweighs the cost in 30 years. Smart village has a large number of advantages and it could bring prosperous society, the project can generate much profitable within 30 years.

Similarly NPV is **Rs 1,550,474,977** at 6.5% discount rate and **Rs 715,758,502.7** at 10% discount rate which is positive. So, the project is accepted.

Also, the IRR of the project is **18.32%** which is almost three times greater than 6.5% which is of *Nepal Rastra Bank* and more than 10% MARR. So the project is accepted.

Hence, from the above result, it can be assured that the quality of life along with economic activities of a village can be improved. So, everyone should be ready to implement this type of project with the improvement of further indicators necessary.

But the above data are all assumed and are from very few limited sources detail economic analysis is beyond the scope of this thesis. So to obtain effective and efficient results detailed economic analysis should be done.

4.3.2 Financing Model

Building up new infrastructure and developing Smart Village requires a proper model of financing. Some of the models of financing are briefly explained below:

A. Tourism Infrastructure Development Project

As a financing model, the Government of Nepal may set up a project for the Tourism Infrastructure Development of that zone. The yearly Budget for the project will develop the area as a tourism center. The local government should initiate this and suggest the central government for the establishment of the project. This generally happens if the project is very important.

B. Yearly budget of Government agency as Municipality or Province government

The Municipality or the Province government may allocate a partial budget every year for the development of the area.

C. Public-Private Partnership Program

This involves a bond between government agencies and private businesses to provide facilities or services to the public. This helps to operate various revenue-generating activities in the village through a number of functions and activities within and around the village.

D. Grants & Donations

Any Grants or Donations from any agency or country may also be an investment for the area. This might be quite difficult for this project but still, it's not impossible.

E. Sole Private Investment

The project can also be implemented by giving it on lease to any private investor for 30-50years as per discussion. The private investor may invest in the area and gain revenue and pay lease to the government as well.

4.3.3 Income Generating Source

The development of Smart villages induces various opportunities for the generation of income. These may be used in the sustainability of the City. Some of the Income generating sources in the village are presented below:

1. Agro-Based Industry
2. Adventure Tourism
3. Cultural Tourism and Homestay
4. Market Commercialization and expansion

4.4 Discussion Using SWOT Analysis on Practicability of Smart Village

SWOT Analysis is a strategic technique for the analysis of Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats in any project or development plan. SWOT analysis of smart village features in the study area is done as in table 4.7:

Table 4.7: SWOT Analysis

SN	Features	Strength	Weakness	Opportunity	Threat
1	Smart Utilization of Resources	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • More than 90% of the land is used for agriculture purposes. • Self-Sustained family. • Kiwi farming, Dairy products, medicinal herbs, etc. are the source of income. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of well-managed irrigation facility. • Lack of proper market. • Lack of employment opportunity. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Construction of dairy processing plants • Development of Agro-Based market • Employment opportunity in factory and market. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor road connectivity • Land plotting • Climate change • Less interest of younger people in agriculture
2	Smart Living	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ease in road access as connected to National Highway in Barbote. • 90% of households have a clean and quality water supply • Management of solid waste at the household level • 100% electricity and 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The absence of blacktopped road and road are not accessed to the household. • Supply of water is only from RVT, no provision of rainwater harvesting • Lack of proper dumping site and no segregation of waste. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National Highway linkage to the municipality • Enough water supply sources can be converted to 100%. • Biogas can be the best option for energy and have enough 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of proper road services so the chance of migration. • There is no proper treatment plant for water supply so the chance of water-borne diseases.

		<p>telecommunication</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of health post and more than 33 schools throughout the municipality 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fluctuation in the supply of electricity due to poor electric poles and poor connectivity. • Lack of college for higher education and absence of facilitated hospital. 	<p>space for a dumping site.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Solar Energy can be the best option for regular electricity. • Educational institutions can be upgraded to higher secondary and under construction of 15 bedded hospital. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pollution of solid and incinerated waste within the entire municipality. • Poor infrastructure for the supply of electricity and poor internet connection. • Challenges in the upgradation of educational institutions due to land availability and poor health education.
3	Smart Governance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Formation of local government. • Having own infrastructure with integration of IT. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of manpower in the office • Services are not provided at the proper time and the website is not updated frequently 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The decision-making power of local representatives • Plan and program don't rely 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Planning is not well optimized. • Not fully Independent.

				mostly on the central government.	
4	Smart Village Services	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rural municipality services and other available services of office are a bit fast due to availability of internet. • Schools are providing computer-based subjects. • Under constructed hospital can start their services online and offline. • Job opportunities can be created in the field of agriculture with digitization. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Services of office are not so fast • Transportation service is not easily available. • It is not sure how long it takes to upgrade schools and hospitals. • Resources available are not utilized properly because of manpower. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ICT center and free Wi-Fi hotspot can be provided • E-government is possible if a fast connection to the internet is provided. • Mobile banking digital payment methods can be integrated. • The establishment of a medicinal herb processing plant can increase income generation. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of fund • Due to topography, it costs more, and not easy to provide a fast connection to the internet. • Digital apps can't be handy to all persons.

5	Smart Technology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Availability of mobile internet, smartphones. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poor coverage of mobile signals and the internet most of the elderly people don't know to use smartphones . 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can strengthen mobile internet, providing proper training and connection of fiber internet. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Topography is the only main reason for the hindrance of infrastructure development.
6	Smart Tourism	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Location of famous religious and tourist site i.e. Maipokhari Ramsar Site • Kiwi Zone of Minister Agriculture Modernization and cultivation of medical herbs. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Hilly topography and infrastructure for tourism are not well managed. • Limited transportation facility. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possibility of the best tourist spot with the availability of the best infrastructures. • The medicinal herb industry can be established. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Animal Trafficking and exploitation of medical herbs
7	Gender Equity and Women Empowerment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • There is no discrimination in providing education to all the gender. • Participation of women in local government. • Women are mostly engaged equally in agriculture, homestay 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • In villages still, child marriage can be found which led girls to drop out of school at an early age. • Although women are engaged in local government, they have not 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enforcement and education can prove girls and boys are equal in all aspects. • The establishment of the agriculture industry can 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Poverty and education are the reasons for women's backwardness. • Poor institutional development plan for

		business, and the cultivation of medicinal herbs.	been treated equally because of a male-dominated society.	provide an opportunity for women to rise.	the right of women.
--	--	---	---	---	---------------------

Chapter 5

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATION

Developing a village into a smart village is not a one-day goal. If the literature from around the world is reviewed, it can be concluded that a smart village is only one step towards development that can provide basic facilities and infrastructure that can solve problems of the village without interfering with village rule and regulation. It just boosts up the village lifestyle so that village people can link directly or indirectly with the world.

5.1 Key Findings

1. From the literature review of various papers, various features were adopted as Smart Utilization of Resources, Smart Living, Smart Governance, Smart Village Services, Smart Technology, Smart Tourism, and Gender Equity and Women Equity.
2. From the questionnaire survey, it was found the majority of respondents supported the perspective of smart village features as fair and individual ratings on smart village feature were given as Fair (2.82), Fair (3.02), Fair (2.93), Fair (3.17), Fair (3.2), Good (2.42) and Poor (3.46) respectively from five-point Likert scale.
3. B/C ratio was found as 4.98 and 2.85 at 6.5% and 10% discount rate, NPV was found as Rs 1,550,474,977 and Rs 715,758,502.7 at 6.5% and 10% discount rate and IRR was found as 18.32 %.

5.2 Conclusion

The research study shows that rural territories are now in the phase of development and the development process is not as fast and effective as expected. To implement the smart village features like Smart Utilization of Resources, Smart Living, Smart Governance, Smart Village Services, Smart Technology, Smart Tourism, and Gender Equity and Women Equity initially, there is a need of proper institutional documents comprising regulatory guidelines which guide every stage of development of the smart village and inspect the indicators or features.

Findings indicate that the rural areas are now on the verge of development as they are recently linked with the national road network, infrastructures like the hospital, school, water supply, irrigation are in the phase of improvement which is making rural life easy. The data shows that children in the village are getting their primary education, women have participated in local government and their condition is not worst. In the field of technology, most of the people have mobile phones, bank account and are enjoying internet facility. With the establishment of the local government, they have developed their plan and policy and are made up of members of the local people who know what is important and necessary in their area, resulting in the local population not being dependent on the central government. Hilly area has its special topography, environment, culture, which can attract local and foreign tourists. But due to lack of proper vision and infrastructures like hotels, transportation, they are not attracting much as they can. Village residents live mostly utilizing local resources, dependent on agriculture but in the old and

traditional way. Day to day life is not easy as compared to urban life but are living in a clean and happy environment. Therefore, the present situation is such that complete development of smart village cannot be achievable as the services and facilities described above don't completely comply with smart village features. With the proper policy, facilities and services which can assure the compliance of indicators and features, we can reach the success of implementation.

Smart Village is not the development of entirely new areas and new infrastructure but it is the sustainable growth of existing villages in a planned way with a definite goal. It is the development and improvement of the economic, social, cultural, and technological aspects of the village. All the economic indicators give us a positive response i.e. it is economically feasible and give a quality life to all the beneficiaries and stakeholders. So, the implementation of a smart village must be done but with the improvement of the features and services mentioned above.

5.3 Recommendation

1. Institutions should adopt minimum indicators or features as Smart Utilization of Resources, Smart Living, Smart Governance, Smart Village Services, Smart Technology, Smart Tourism, and Gender Equity and Women Equity.
2. Proper training, guidance and user education must be provided to the consumers, stakeholders and implementing agency to overcome the incompetence of indicators or features.
3. Smart Village is economically successful from the above result and is an investment toward achieving improvement in quality of life rather than recovery of investment as there is a future of the smart village.
4. Proper and sufficient security arrangements shall be made for the safety of visitors, existing biodiversity, and components of the area with cultural values.
5. Detailed survey, specific study, soil investigation is necessary before implementation of any plan and program.
6. Necessary by-laws act, a legal framework for carrying out various work is needed to be developed by the province and local government.

5.4 Recommendation for Further Study

1. Smart Village is a concept adopted by developed nations so there must be much more planning, study, and homework before implementation of any projects.
2. Every village has different characteristics, so the development model of one village could be only a reference for the further analysis of a particular village.

REFERENCES

1. MOFAGA,2021.Kathmandu, Nepal: Ministry of Federal Affairs and General Administration (MOFAGA). Available at:<https://www.mofaga.gov.np/>
2. Mishra, Anjay & Shah, Surendra. ,2018. Estimating Housing Unit for Low Income Group of People in Kathmandu, Nepal. NOLEGEIN-Journal of Operations Research & Management. 1. 16-27. 10.37591/njorm.v1i2.185.Available at: [\(PDF\) Estimating Housing Unit for Low Income Group of People in Kathmandu, Nepal \(researchgate.net\)](#)
3. J. Ahlawat, 2017. Smart Villages, Information Communication Technology and Geographical Information System. *International Journal of Current Trends in Science and Technology*, vol. 7. No. 8, pp. 20232–20238.
4. UN,2015. *Transforming our World: The 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development*. New York, USA: United Nations(UN). Accessible at:<https://sustainabledevelopment.un.org/post2015/transformingourworld/>
5. UN,2020. *Sustainable Development Goals Report 2020*. New York, USA: United Nations(UN). Available at: [The-Sustainable-Development-Goals-Report-2020.pdf \(un.org\)](#) [Assessed on Jan 28, 2021].
6. N. Viswanadham and S. Vedula, 2010 .Design of Smart Villages.ISB: The Centre for Global Logistics and Manufacturing Strategies. Available at:<https://gtl.csa.iisc.ac.in/nv/Mypublications/C/z.pdf>
7. Poudel, 2013. NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT PLAN AND URBANIZATION IN NEPAL. Available at: [\(PDF\) NATIONAL DEVELOPMENT PLAN AND URBANIZATION IN NEPAL \(researchgate.net\)](#)
8. P. Abinash and J. Josephine, 2018. Internet of Things (IoT) for Smart Village. *International Conference on Advancements in Engineering, Technology and Sciences (ICAETS)*, pp. 813– 819.
9. ITU,2020. *Building Smart Villages: A Blueprint. 2020*. Geneva, Switzerland: International Telecommunication Union (ITU) Available at: https://www.itu.int/dms_pub/itu-d/opb/str/D-STR-SMART_VILLAGE.NIGER-2020-PDF-E.pdf[Assessed on Oct 15, 2020].
10. ENRD,2019. *Smart Villages: A new concept for rural development, 2019*. Congleton, United Kingdom. The European Network for Rural Development (ENRD). Available at: <https://www.scitecheuropa.eu/smart-villages-rural-development/95112/>
11. S. Vanderklei, 2019. *The role of Geospatial Technologies in Building Smarter Cities*. Master. Utrecht Sustainability Institute/Municipality of Utrecht, Utrecht.
12. E.Stojmenova, et.al, 2018. Smart Villages: Comprehensive Review of Initiatives and Practices. *Sustainability*. 10. 2559. 10.3390/su10072559.
13. Freshwater, 2000. “The Promotion of Employment and Economic Development,” in TVA Rural Studies Program, Potsdam, Germany, June 2000.
14. Rutuja, et.al, 2016. “Study and Development of Village as a Smart Village”.*International Journal of Scientific & Engineering Research*, Volume 7, Issue 6, June-2016 ISSN 2229-

5518. Accessible at: <https://www.ijser.org/onlineResearchPaperViewer.aspx?Study-and-development-of-village-as-a-smart-village.pdf>[Assessed on Oct 12, 2020].
15. Kulkarni, 2015. Clean and Smart Village: Aspects and Alternatives, *International Journal of Research in Engineering, Science and Technologies – Civil Engineering*, ISSN 2395-6453, Vol. 1, No. 3, June 2015, PP 19-23, Retrieved from: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/289685973_Clean_Village_and_Project_Based_Learning
 16. Z. Zhao, 2009. "Research on the Beijing Rural Village Classification & Development under Urbanization." *The 4th International Conference of the International Forum on Urbanism (IFoU), Beijing, China, 2009*, pp. 1387-1394.
 17. Patel. B, Shah. R, 2017. "Smart village a case study of Kolavada village." *International Journal of Advanced Research in Science and Engineering*, Vol.No.04, Issue 12 December-2017. Available at: <https://www.irjet.net/archives/V4/i12/IRJET-V4I12171.pdf> [Assessed on Oct 12, 2020].
 18. CBS, 2012. *National population and housing census 2011*. Kathmandu, Nepal: Central Bureau of Statistics (CBS).Retrieved from: <https://cbs.gov.np/>
 19. Aziiza, A, and T D Susanto,2020. "The Smart Village Model for Rural Area (Case Study: Banyuwangi Regency)." *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* 722 (January 21, 2020): 012011. Accessed at: <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/722/1/012011>
 20. Eco Needs Foundation, 2016. "Smart Village: Smart Village Dhanora Is the New Model of Village Development." *Smart Village*, [Blog] August 29, 2016. Accessed from: <https://smartvillagedhanora.blogspot.com/2016/08/smart-village-dhanora-is-new-model-of.html>.> [Accessed 20 Jan 2021].
 21. Harijan, 1922.Gandhi's Views & Work for Village Development Panchayat Raj. *Gandhi-Manibhavan*,[Online]. Retrieved from:< <http://www.gandhi-manibhavan.org/>>
 22. Smart Villages,2020. New Thinking for Off-Grid Communities Worldwide.*Smartvillage*,[Online]. Available on: <http://e4sv.org/about-us/what-are-smart-villages/> [Assessed on Dec 25, 2020].
 23. IEEE,2020. IEEE Smart Village,2020. *Smartvillage.ieee*,[Online]. Available on: <http://ieee-smart-village.org/>[Assessed on Dec 25, 2020].
 24. Holmes, J. et al., 2017. The Smart Villages Initiative: Findings 2014–2017; The Smart Villages Initiative: Cambridge, UK. Available at: [The-Smart-Villages-Initiative-Findings-2014-2017_web.pdf \(e4sv.org\)](http://www.e4sv.org/The-Smart-Villages-Initiative-Findings-2014-2017_web.pdf) [Assessed on Dec 28, 2020].
 25. O. Adegboyega & J. Tomasz, 2010. A whole-of-government approach to information technology strategy management. 72-81.Available at: https://www.researchgate.net/publication/262169576_Whole-of-government_approach_to_information_technology_strategy_management_Building_a_sustainable_collaborative_technology_environment_in_government

26. Boontham N, et al.,2015; Smart Village A Sustainable Model for Community Development: Available at:
http://www.bhutanstudies.org.bt/2015GNHConference/Paperfor2015GNHConference/9.SMART%20Village_Noppawan.pdf
27. R. Pinak et.al, 2015. “SMART VILLAGES THROUGH INFORMATION TECHNOLOGY – NEED OF EMERGING INDIA.” *IPASJ International Journal of Information Technology (IJIT)*. 3. 1-6.Retrieved from:
https://www.researchgate.net/profile/Pinak-Ranade/publication/280613118_SMART_VILLAGES_THROUGH_INFORMATION_TECHNOLOGY_-_NEED_OF_EMERGING_INDIA/links/55beedf008aec0e5f445e5a1/SMART-VILLAGES-THROUGH-INFORMATION-TECHNOLOGY-NEED-OF-EMERGING-INDIA.pdf
28. Clancy, J. S., Winther, T., Matinga, M. N., & Oparaocha, S., 2012. Gender equity in access to and benefits from modern energy and improved energy technologies: world development report background paper. *ETC/ENERGIA in association Nord/Sør-konsulentene*. Retrieved From: [Gender equity in access to and benefits from modern energy and improved energy technologies: world development report background paper | Paper | Microsoft Academic](#)
29. A.Shahid, et.al, 2020. “Review on Development of Smart Villages” *International Journal of Scientific Research in Science and Technology*, Volume 5, Issue 7, Print ISSN: 2395-6011 | Online ISSN: 2395-602X
30. Atkočiūnienė, 2019. "Smart Village Development Principles and Driving Forces: The Case of Lithuania" *European Countryside*, vol.11, no.4, 2019, pp.497-516.Retrieved From: <https://doi.org/10.2478/euco-2019-0028>
31. Thapa,2010. Village Tourism Development & Management in Nepal: A Case Study of Sirubari Village. *Ecoclub* [online], Retrieved From: <https://ecoclub.com/education/articles/488-sirubari-village-tourism-nepal> [Accessed 17 Jun 2021].
32. Reeves, H. and Baden, S., 2000.” Gender and Development: Concepts and Definitions.” *Prepared for the Department for International Development (DFID)*. Brighton, UK: BRIDGE, Institute of Development Studies.
33. McGill, 1996.” Defining Institutional Development (ID)”. In: *Institutional Development*. Palgrave Macmillan, London. Retrieved from: https://doi.org/10.1007/978-1-349-25071-4_1
34. Creighton, James L.,2005. “The public participation handbook: making better decisions through citizen involvement”.ISBN 0-7879-7307-6 (alk. paper). 1. Political participation. The United States. Handbooks, manuals, etc. Available at:
<https://smartnet.niua.org/sites/default/files/resources/Public%20Participation%20Handboo>

- [k.pdf](#)
35. MOFAGA,2017.*Local Self Governance Act 1999*. Ministry of Federal Affairs and General Administration (MOFAGA).Law Books Management Board, Nepal. Available at:<https://www.lawcommission.gov.np/en/wp-content/uploads/2018/10/local-self-governance-act-2055-1999.pdf>
 36. Nepal Law Commission,2007. *Land Acquisition Act 2034*.Nepal Law Commission, Nepal. Available at: [Land Acquisition Act, 2034 \(1977\) – Nepal Law Commission](#)
 37. Gupta, K.,2009. Cost management: Measuring, monitoring& motivating performance. Global India Publications.
 38. Xiangyuan, 2018. *COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS OF SMART CITIES TECHNOLOGIES AND APPLICATIONS*. Master of Civil Engineering. University of Delaware
 39. Patrick, M. and French, N. 2016, "The internal rate of return (IRR): projections, benchmarks and pitfalls", *Journal of Property Investment & Finance*, Vol. 34 No. 6, pp. 664-669. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JPIF-07-2016-0059>
 40. SRM,2020.*Sandakpur Rural Municipality Profile 2020*.Sandakpur Rural Municipality(SRM).Ilam, Nepal. Retrieved From: [सन्दकपुर गाउँपालिका, गाँउ कार्यपालिकाको कार्यालय | प्रदेश नं - १, ईलाम, नेपाल \(sandakpurmun.gov.np\)](#)
 41. K C, Surendra & Khanal, Samir & Shrestha, Prachand & Lamsal, Buddhi., 2011. Current status of renewable energy in Nepal: Opportunities and challenges. *Renewable and Sustainable Energy Reviews*. 15. 4107–4117. 10.1016/j.rser.2011.07.022. Retrieved From: [Current status of renewable energy in Nepal: Opportunities and challenges | Request PDF \(researchgate.net\)](#)

APPENDICES

Appendix A: Respondent Opinion on Smart Village Features

S.N	Respondent	Smart Utilization of Resources	Smart Living	Smart Governance	Smart Village Services	Smart Technology	Smart Tourism	Gender Equity and Women Empowerment
1	Tilchan Khatiwoda	3	2	3	3	3	3	2
2	Sukaraj Rai	3	3	3	2	2	3	3
3	Tanka Kumar Gautaula	3	3	2	3	4	4	5
4	Gajhadar Khatiwoda	3	3	3	2	3	3	3
5	Niroj Khatiwoda	3	5	3	4	5	3	3
6	Tara Nath Subedi	4	3	3	3	3	3	3
7	Ram Bahadur Rai	3	3	2	4	5	3	3
8	Toran Subedi	3	2	3	4	3	3	3
9	Netra Subedi	3	4	2	4	4	3	3
10	Khem Prasad Khatiwoda	3	3	2	3	2	3	3
11	Giriraj Mani Khanal	3	3	3	3	3	4	4
12	Ramesh Subedi	3	2	3	3	2	3	3
13	Tularam Gurung	3	3	3	3	2	3	4
14	Prakash Rai	3	3	2	3	3	2	3
15	Bhim Prasad Khatiwoda	3	3	3	3	3	3	4
16	Lal Bahadur Gurung	3	3	3	3	3	3	4
17	Nawang Rai	2	2	2	2	2	2	3
18	Yadav Rai	3	3	3	3	3	3	3

19	Dhanapati Rai	3	2	3	3	2	3	3
20	Roshan Bhattarai	5	5	4	5	5	3	5
21	Kishor Rai	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
22	Ashok Aangdamb e	2	3	2	3	3	3	4
23	Mohan Kumar Rai	2	4	2	2	3	3	3
24	Baburam Naupane	2	3	3	4	3	2	3
25	Ashok Bhattarai	2	2	5	2	3	3	3
26	Rahar Kumar Rai	2	2	1	2	3	2	2
27	Lila Bahadur Rai	2	3	3	3	4	2	3
28	Tularam Gurung	2	3	4	3	3	2	3
29	Yubaraj Poudel	2	3	3	3	3	1	4
30	Prem Tshiring Rai	2	3	4	3	3	3	4
31	Yam Bahadur Rai	3	3	3	3	3	2	3
32	Dhan Prakash Rai	2	2	3	3	3	2	3
33	Mohan Bantawa Rai	4	4	4	3	4	2	4
34	Jiwan Seewa	2	3	4	4	3	1	3
35	Dang Kumar Rai	2	4	2	3	4	1	4
36	Raj Bahadur Rai	4	4	4	4	4	2	5
37	Mohan Bantawa Rai	3	3	3	3	3	1	3

38	Jiwan Khimding	3	4	3	4	3	1	4
39	Debendra Subedi	4	4	3	4	4	1	5
40	Ratan Rai	3	4	4	4	3	1	5
41	Giriraj Khanal	3	3	4	4	3	1	4
42	Sandesh Dhamala	2	1	2	3	3	4	3
43	Kul Bahadur Rai	3	2	3	3	3	4	3
44	Rupen Nembyang	3	4	2	3	4	1	4
45	Lila Bahadur Rai	3	2	3	4	4	1	4
TOTAL		127	136	132	143	144	109	156

Appendix B: Questionnaires

8/4/2021

सन्दकपुर गाउँपालिकाको वस्तुगत विवरण

सन्दकपुर गाउँपालिकाको वस्तुगत विवरण

नमस्कार !

म रजत पोखरेल , म हाल पोखरा विश्वबिधालय अन्तरगत MSc in Construction Management अध्ययनरत विद्यार्थी हु । नेपाल को पहाडी छेत्रका गाउँ मा स्मार्ट भिलेजको रुपमा विकास गर्न सक्ने संभ्याबता अध्ययन गर्ने हेतुले यो प्रश्नावली हजुरसमक्ष पेश गरेको छु । प्राप्त जानकारी गोप्य राखिने र शैक्षिक उद्देश्यको लागि मात्र प्रयोग हुने व्यहोरा आश्वस्त पार्दै हजुरको समयको लागि धन्यवाद ज्ञापन गर्दछु ।

* Required

1. नाम : *

2. ठेगाना : *

3. अतिरिक्त विवरण

स्मार्ट नागरिक

यस खण्डमा तपाइको व्यक्तिगत तथा पारिवारिक विवरण उपलब्ध गराइदिनुहोला ।

4. तपाइँको परिवारमा कति जना सदस्य छन ? *

5. परिवारमा सामान्य लेखपढ गर्न सक्ने सदस्य कति जना छन ? *

Mark only one oval.

- छैनन्
 ५० % भन्दा कम
 ५० % भन्दा बढी
 सबै

6. परिवारका सबै बालबालिका स्कुल जान्छन ? *

Mark only one oval.

- जान्छन
 जादैनन्

7. परिवारमा माध्यमिक तह उत्तीर्ण सदस्य कति जना छन ? *

Mark only one oval.

- छैनन्
 ५० % भन्दा कम
 ५० % भन्दा बढी
 सबै

8. परिवारमा आर्थिक रुपले सक्रिय सदस्य कति जना छन ? *

Mark only one oval.

- छैनन्
 ५० % भन्दा कम
 ५० % भन्दा बढी
 सबै

9. परिवारमा आर्थिक रूपले सक्रिय महिला सदस्य छन ? *

Mark only one oval.

- छन
 छैनन्

10. तपाईंको परिवारमा दीर्घरोगी सदस्य कति जना छन ? *

Mark only one oval.

- छैनन्
 ५० % भन्दा कम
 ५० % भन्दा बढी
 सबै

11. तपाईंको परिवारमा मोबाइल/कम्प्युटर /इन्टरनेट प्रयोग गर्न सक्ने सदस्य कति छन ? *

Mark only one oval.

- छैनन्
 ५० % भन्दा कम
 ५० % भन्दा बढी
 सबै

12. तपाईंको घरपयेक स्वास्थ्यसंस्था को सेवा सुविधा कस्तो छ ?

Mark only one oval.

- राम्रो
 नराम्रो
 Other: _____

स्मार्ट शासन

यस खण्डमा तपाईंको स्थानीय सरकारबाट उपलब्ध सेवाहरुको विवरण उपलब्ध गराइदिनुहोला ।

13. तपाईंको घर बाट वार्ड कार्यलय पुग्न कति समय लाग्छ ?

14. तपाईंको घर बाट गाउँपालिका कार्यलय पुग्न कति समय लाग्छ ?

15. तपाईंको घर बाट वार्ड कार्यलय कसरी जानुहुन्छ ?

Mark only one oval.

पैदल

गाडी

Other: _____

16. तपाईंको घर बाट गाउँपालिका कार्यलय कसरी जानुहुन्छ ?

Mark only one oval.

पैदल

गाडी

Other: _____

17. वार्ड कार्यलयबाट पाउने सेवा सुविधा कतिको छिटो छ ? *

Mark only one oval.

- छिटो छ
- ढिलो छ
- Other: _____

18. गाउँपालिका कार्यलयबाट पाउने सेवा सुविधा कतिको छिटो छ ? *

Mark only one oval.

- छिटो छ
- ढिलो छ
- Other: _____

19. वार्ड कार्यलयबाट पाउने सेवा सुविधा के के छन्? *

20. गाउँपालिका कार्यलयबाट पाउने सेवा सुविधा के के छन्? *

21. गाउँपालिकाको विकासमा गाउँपालिका कार्यलयको पारदर्शीता छ कि छैन ? *

Mark only one oval.

छ

छैन

Other: _____

22. गाउँपालिका कार्यलयले तपाईंहरूलाई आबस्यक जानकारी उपलब्ध गराउछ कि गराउदैन ? *

Mark only one oval.

गराउछ

गराउदैन

Other: _____

23. तपाईंहरूले समूह मा बसेर गाउँ पालिकाको विकास निर्माण वा अन्य कुनै काम गर्नु भयेको छ ? *

Mark only one oval.

छ

छैन

छ भने भन्नु होओस

Other: _____

स्मार्ट भौतिक सम्राचना

यस खण्डमा तपाइलाई उपलब्ध भौतिक सम्राचनाका विवरण उपलब्ध गराइदिनुहोला ।

24. तपाईंको घर छेत्र मा गाडी पुग्छ कि पुग्दैन ?

Mark only one oval.

- पुग्छ
 पुग्दैन
 Other: _____

25. तपाईंको घर पुग्ने बाटो कस्तो छ ? *

Mark only one oval.

- कच्ची
 ग्रावेल
 पक्क
 Other: _____

26. तपाईंको घरमा पानी कसरि आउछ ? घर नजकै लिन जानु पर्छ भने कति मिटर टाडा छ ?

Mark only one oval.

- घरमा नै धारा छ
 घर नजकै लिन जानु पर्छ
 Other: _____

27. तपाईंको घरमा पानी कति समय सम्म आउछ ? *

Mark only one oval.

- २४ घण्टा आउछ
 दिन मा १ चोटी आउछ
 दिन मा २ चोटी आउछ
 Other: _____

28. पानी को बिल तिर्नु पर्छ कि पर्दैन ?

Mark only one oval.

- पर्छ
 पर्दैन
 Other: _____

29. शौचालय कच्ची कि पक्कि छ ? *

Mark only one oval.

- कच्ची
 पक्कि
 शौचालय नै छैन

30. ढल निकास तथा बर्खा को पानी को ब्यबस्था छ कि छैन ? *

Mark only one oval.

- छ
 छैन

31. बिजुली बत्ति छ कि छैन ? छैन भने किन र के प्रयोग गर्नु हुन्छ त्येशको विकल्प मा ? *

Mark only one oval.

- छ
 छैन
 Other: _____

32. बिजुली बत्ति के के मा प्रयोग गर्नु हुन्छ ?

33. WIFI को प्रयोग गर्नु हुन्छ घरमा ? प्रयोग गर्नु हुन्छ भने कति खर्च हुन्छ महिनामा ? *

Mark only one oval.

- गर्छु
- गर्दिन
- Other: _____

34. मोबाइल इन्टरनेट प्रयोग गर्नु हुन्छ ? प्रयोग गर्दा कति खर्च हुन्छ महिना मा ? *

Mark only one oval.

- गर्छु
- गर्दिन
- Other: _____

35. तपाइको घरपायक ठाउँ मा बैंक छ कि छैन ? तपाइको बैंकमा खाता छ कि छैन ? *

Mark only one oval.

- बैंक छ तर खाता छैन
- बैंक पनि छ खाता पनि छ
- बैंक पनि छैन खाता पनि छैन
- Other: _____

36. मोबाइल बैंकिंगको प्रयोग गर्नु हुन्छ ? *

Mark only one oval.

- गर्छु
 गर्दिन
 Other: _____

37. मोबाइल फोन को सिग्नल राम्ररी आउँछ ? कुन सिम कार्ड प्रयोग गर्नु हुन्छ ? *

Mark only one oval.

- आउछ
 आउदैन
 Other: _____

38. मोबाइल इन्टरनेट राम्ररी चल्छ कि चल्दैन ? कुन सिम कार्ड प्रयोग गर्नु हुन्छ इन्टरनेट चलाउन ? *

Mark only one oval.

- चल्छ
 चल्दैन
 Other: _____

39. खान पकाउन के को प्रयोग गर्नु हुन्छ ? *

Mark only one oval.

- दाउरा
 ग्यास
 Other: _____

40. तपाइको घर कस्तो खाल को छ ? *

Mark only one oval.

- खर को छाना भएको माटो र ढुंगा को
- टीन को छाना भएको माटो र ढुंगा को
- टीन को छाना भएको सिमेन्ट र ढुंगा को
- टीन को छाना भएको सिमेन्ट र इट्टा को
- पक्कि
- Other: _____

41. तपाइको घर भूकम्प प्रतिरोध छ कि छैन ? *

Mark only one oval.

- छ
- छैन
- Other: _____

42. तपाइको बसोबास क्षेत्र पैरो र भुछय को जोखिम मा छ कि छैन ? *

Mark only one oval.

- छ
- छैन
- Other: _____

43. तपाइले नजिक को स्वस्थ केन्द्र वा हस्पिटल बाट कस्तो सुविधा लिन पाउनु हुन्छ ?

44. तपाईका छोरा छोरि ले बिद्यालयमा computer को प्रयोग गर्छन कि गर्दैनन् ? *

Mark only one oval.

- गर्छन
- गर्दैनन्
- थाह भएन
- Other: _____

45. तपाई बस्ने छेत्र कत्तिको सुरक्छित छ ? चोरि हिंशा हुन्छ कि हुदैन ? *

Mark only one oval.

- सुरक्छित छ
- सुरक्छित छैन
- छिटफुट घटना हुन्छन
- Other: _____

स्मार्ट इकोनोमी

यस खण्डमा तपाइको आर्थिक विवरण उपलब्ध गराइदिनुहोला ।

46. घर मा तपाईं मात्रै कमाउने हो ? हैन भने अरु कतिजना काम गर्नु हुन्छ ? *

Mark only one oval.

- हो
- हैन
- Other: _____

47. तपाइको पेशा वा मुख्य आम्दानी को श्रोत के हो ? *

48. तपाईंले गर्ने पेशा ले एस ठाउँ मा बर्षदिन खान बस्र पुग्छ?

Mark only one oval.

- पुग्छ
- पुग्दैन
- Other: _____

49. तपाईं रोजगारी को सिलसिला मा एस ठाउँ बाट बाहिर काम गर्नु हुन्छ कि येही ठाउँ मा ? *

Mark only one oval.

- एस ठाउँ बाट बाहिर
- येही ठाउँ मा
- Other: _____

50. तपाइको छेत्र मा रोजगारी को आवसर छ कि छैन ? *

Mark only one oval.

- छ
- छैन
- Other: _____

51. तपाइको कृषि योग्य जमिन छ कि छैन ? छ वने कति जति छ होला ?

Mark only one oval.

- छ
- छैन
- Other: _____

52. येश ठाउँ को मुख्य आर्थिक श्रोत का केन्द्र वा श्रोत के के हुन् ?

53. येश ठाउँ को मुख्य बिसेसता के हो ?

54. येश ठाउँ बाट बसाई सराई रोक्न र येही बस्न सक्ने र कमाउने बाताबरण गर्न के गर्नु पर्ला ?

Additional Data

Likert scale:1=Excellent,2=Good,3=Fair,4=Poor,5=Very Poor

55. Smart Utilization of resources

Mark only one oval.

1	2	3	4	5
<input type="radio"/>				

56. Smart Living

Mark only one oval.

1	2	3	4	5
<input type="radio"/>				

57. Smart Governance

Mark only one oval.

1	2	3	4	5
<input type="radio"/>				

58. Smart Village Services

Mark only one oval.

1	2	3	4	5
<input type="radio"/>				

59. Smart Technology

Mark only one oval.

1	2	3	4	5
<input type="radio"/>				

60. Tourism

Mark only one oval.

1	2	3	4	5
<input type="radio"/>				

61. Gender Equity and women empowerment

Mark only one oval.

1	2	3	4	5
<input type="radio"/>				

62. END

This content is neither created nor endorsed by Google.

Google Forms

Appendix C: Observed Frequency and Expected Frequency for Chi-Square Test

	Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor	Very Poor	Grand Total
Observed Frequency						
Smart Utilization Of Resources	0	14	26	4	1	45
Smart Living	1	10	23	9	2	45
Smart Governance	1	11	24	8	1	45
Smart Village Services	0	6	26	12	1	45
Smart Technology	0	6	27	9	3	45
Tourism	10	10	21	4	0	45
Gender Equity and Women Empowerment	0	2	25	13	5	45
Grand Total	12	59	172	59	13	315

Here, Expected Frequency=(R1 Total*C1 Total)/Grand Total and so on.

Expected Frequency	Excellent	Good	Fair	Poor	Very Poor	Grand Total
Smart Utilization Of Resources	1.714285714	8.428571	24.5714	8.429	1.857	45
Smart Living	1.714285714	8.428571	24.5714	8.429	1.857	45
Smart Governance	1.714285714	8.428571	24.5714	8.429	1.857	45
Smart Village Services	1.714285714	8.428571	24.5714	8.429	1.857	45
Smart Technology	1.714285714	8.428571	24.5714	8.429	1.857	45
Tourism	1.714285714	8.428571	24.5714	8.429	1.857	45
Gender Equity and Women Empowerment	1.714285714	8.428571	24.5714	8.429	1.857	45
Grand Total	12	59	172	59	13	315
chi square p-value	1.39577E-07<0.05			Null Hypothesis Rejected		

Appendix D: Some Pictures and Photograph

Imagined Smart Village Street

School Building

ICT Centre

Hospital

Imagined Village Market Area after 30Years

Sandakpur Village

House

House

Homestay

Maipokhari Ramsar Site Map

Maipokhari

Temple

School

Deurali Bazar

Rock Garden

Village and Road